

A Case for Babylonian Moses

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The biblical birth story of Moses (Exod 2:1-10) shares essential details with the Birth Legend of Sargon, written in Akkadian cuneiform. Although scholars commonly attribute the similarities to the diffusion of the same myths across the Fertile Crescent in antiquity, textual analysis demonstrates that the Hebrew story was adapted from the cuneiform account. A comparison of the scribal acts of naming reveals an intricate interplay between Hebrew words and cuneiform ideographic concepts in the composite text. This signals direct text-to-text derivation rather than oral transmission. The Sargonic source account was most likely composed in the late 8th century BC, which necessitates a radical reevaluation of the traditional timeline of Moses. The Mosaic author's command of this Akkadian source reveals sophisticated cuneiform skills, connecting the composition to the Babylonian exile and the training of talented young Judeans in the language and literature of Chaldea (Dan 1:3-4). The main characters in this story—and in related biblical accounts—resemble influential figures in mid-6th century Babylonia. This in turn suggests that the Hebraic adaptation was originally conceptualized as a ritual invocation of the escape of the captive nation from Neo-Babylon, which is allegorically disguised as ancient Egypt.

Keywords: Akkadian, Allegory, Babylonian exile, Cuneiform, Hebrew Bible, Magical rituals, Mesopotamian myth, Paronomasia, Polysemy, Semiotics, Textual history, Wordplay

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Introduction

The reign of Sargon the Great (c. 2300 BC) pre-dates the era of Moses in the biblical timeline (c. 1300 BC) by a thousand years. The Legend of Sargon (written in Sumerian, c. 1800 BC, Old Babylonian era) describes his divinely-aided rise to power but lacks his birth story.¹ The Birth Legend of Sargon (written in Akkadian) briefly recapitulates Sargon's reign, with much of the tablet devoted to the enigmatic account of the future king placed in a basket in the river as an infant.² The oldest known birth legend tablets are Neo-Assyrian—discovered in the library of Ashurbanipal at Nineveh.³ Although the Neo-Assyrian texts postdate the era of Moses, narrative setting does not establish textual age.

The oldest known Hebrew manuscript recording Moses' birth story is a Dead Sea scroll dating from the Hasmonean era (mid to late second century BC), written in the post-exilic Aramaic script.⁴ The oldest known Sargonic text is approximately 500 years older than the oldest Mosaic text (7th vs. 2nd centuries BC). Despite the conventional assumption that Moses

¹ Cooper and Heimpel, 1983.

² Lewis, 1980.

³ According to William Hallow (2020, p. 48), the Birth Legend of Sargon was composed in the late 8th century BC “to celebrate the triumphs of his namesake, Sargon II.”

⁴ 4Q1, dated by epigraphy (see Tigchelaar, 2023). Another scroll, 4Q11 (written in the Old Hebrew script) has been variously dated between the 3rd and 1st centuries BC (Dayfani, 2021), but only retains two words from the birth story.

lived in the latter half of the 2nd millennium BC and that his story was well known in pre-exilic Israel, we do not possess epigraphic evidence for this. In fact, we have no evidence at all of early Moses beyond his narrative setting. Moreover, no Hebrew scriptures predating the deportation of the population of Judah to Babylon (beginning about 604 BC) have been discovered.⁵

The emergence of Moses (מֹשֶׁה—*mšh*) as the towering figure of Judaism is an historical conundrum. The Old Hebrew analog of his name (𐤎𐤍𐤏) has never been found in archaeological excavations of ancient sites in Israel, Egypt or the interlying desert region. The name Moses is not attested in a trove of correspondence discovered in the ruins of the 5th century BC Judean community in Elephantine in Upper Egypt. After translating more than sixty Aramaic papyri, Arthur Crowley reached an unexpected conclusion: “*So far as we learn from these texts, Moses might never have existed, there might have been no bondage in Egypt, no exodus.*”⁶ This sense is underscored by the worship of the goddess Anat alongside Yahweh in Elephantine—despite the supposed Egyptian setting of the birth of monolatrous Yahwism.⁷

In a recent review, Yonatan Adler concluded that the public observance of the Mosaic Law is not clearly detectable in the archaeological record of Israel before the Hasmonean era (c. 140 BC).⁸ If ordinary Judeans knew of Moses, they did not have a sense of the binding nature of the Mosaic commandments until several centuries after the return of the exiles from Babylon. Thus, from a strictly material viewpoint, we cannot assume Moses’ antiquity.

⁵ To date, the Ketef Hinom grave amulets (c. 600 BC) constitute the sole archaeological find of a pre-exilic scriptural analog. Although they are inscribed with phrases also found in the Priestly Benediction (Num 6:24-26), the phrases are interwoven with others in incantations to ward off evil. This apotropaic context archaeologically predates the oldest known text of Numbers by several centuries.

⁶ Crowley, 1923, p. xxiii.

⁷ The Judean community in Elephantine had a temple in which the deities *yhw* and *ʿnt-yhw* received sacrifices. A temple coin (YHD 24) from Persian era Jerusalem bears the images of Athena (the Greek homolog of Anath) and her owl messenger along with the name of the high priest Yohanan (see Adler, 2022, pp. 198-205). These cultural markers from Elephantine and near contemporary Jerusalem signal that goddess-worship was deeply embedded in Judean religious practice despite accounts of periodic anti-goddess (or more likely aniconic) reforms (see 1 Kgs 15:13, 2 Kgs 23:6-15, Jer 44:17-23).

⁸ Adler (2022, pp. 167-169) notes that Sabbath prohibitions, fasting on Yom Kippur and the depiction of the seven-branched menorah first appear under Hasmonean rule.

The order of events in the account of Moses' birth (Exod 2:1-10) precisely parallels the narrative sequence in the Birth Legend of Sargon, although the geographic setting and the names of the characters differ. Both feature an infant hero who is hidden by his birth mother in a sealed reed basket and placed in the river, then rescued by a substitute parent.⁹ Although the scholarly literature predominantly views the two as semi-autonomous exemplars of the foundling child myth, this presumes an ancient folkloric Moses.² However, the name משה is attested only after the exile. Given the existence of a substantially older text in the literary repertoire of the Mesopotamians who conquered the Fertile Crescent, the *a priori* probability is that the Birth Legend of Sargon inspired its Mosaic counterpart. This raises the possibility that the birth story of Moses indeed marks his debut as a Hebrew folk-hero.

Scribal Invocation and Magical Double-entendres

Like all the patriarchs and matriarchs of the Bible, Moses' name is narratively connected to a meaning expressed through wordplay. Given the Mesopotamian setting of the Genesis beginning, we must consider the influence of the literary techniques common to this region. In classical Mesopotamian works, the act of naming deploys hidden meanings for magical purposes. The archetype of this scribal expression is widely considered to be the *Enuma Elish*, the national epic of Babylon.¹⁰ As observed by Benjamin Foster,

The poem begins and ends with concepts of naming ... For the poet, the name, properly understood, discloses the significance of the created thing. Semantic and phonological analysis of names could lead to understanding of the things named. Names, for this poet, are a text to be read by the informed.¹¹

The cuneiform writing system was developed by the Sumerians and later adopted by the Akkadians, who used the same symbols to represent their language. Hence, Akkadian cuneiform texts have the potential to express Sumerian ideas retained in the same signs. Each sign

⁹ Carroll, 1985, p. 776, argues that the drawing forth of Moses essentially reprises Sargon's story.

¹⁰ See Bottéro, 1992, pp. 32-33, 88-91, 229.

¹¹ Foster, 2005, pp. 437-438.

potentially represents several different phonemes (accreted over time), while a given phoneme may be indicated by several different signs. Modern cuneiform scholars distinguish the sign/sound/idea variants by transcribing them with Latin characters bearing different numerical subscripts.

As explained by Avigdor Hurowitz, “every word could be written in a variety of ways and each sign had a potential of bearing numerous ... readings.” This property of cuneiform “afforded Mesopotamian scribes unique levels of playing on written forms of words unavailable to scribes writing languages that employed alphabetic scripts.”¹² For readers who have not studied cuneiform, this polyvalency can be disorienting. What is important to understand is the unrivalled capacity of cuneiform to encode hidden meanings. This property undergirds the scribal use of cuneiform signs to transmit both a simple surface meaning and deeper matters hidden beneath. The scribes’ awareness of this cryptic duality is attested in the Akkadian terms *lumāšu* (twin-image), *amāt niširti* (hidden word), *niširti ummâni* (hidden lore of the scholars) and *pirištu ša ilī* (secrets of the gods).¹³

The most skilled Mesopotamian scribes made use of the inherent property of cuneiform signs to express ideas (called *logograms*) and sounds (called *syllabograms*) at the same time.¹⁰ This gave them a powerful toolbox for effecting textual magic. A scribe’s deciphering of a profound symbolic meaning was understood as a revelation from the gods who gifted humans with the arch-craft of pressing signs into the primordial clay of creation. A master scribe could discern destiny by deciphering the cryptic symbolism of hallowed works from earlier eras.¹⁰ It follows, then, that a scribe could alter destiny by recognizing and establishing an alternate reading of the signs. This scribal overturning of fate had to be “true”—that is, its derivation had to fit the master pattern of the myth in which it was found.¹⁴ It also had to harmonize with the wishes and the known character of the particular god(s) invoked.¹⁵

¹² Hurowitz, 2020, p. 66.

¹³ See Landsberger and Kinnier Wilson (1961), McHugh (2017) and Noegel (2021).

¹⁴ The term “myth” here follows Samuel Noah Kramer’s simple definition as “*stories in which the gods* (plural) *play the most important roles*” (Kramer and Maier, 1989, p. 154).

¹⁵ For example, the decree of Enlil concerning the Deluge (meant to destroy all life) was circumvented by Ea, who (via the authoring scribe) instructed the flood hero to construct a vessel filled with two of each creature—in keeping with the god’s identity as benevolent creator of life and author of clever schemes.

In contradistinction to oral folklore recorded in writing (such as the Grimm brothers' *Hausmärchen*). Mesopotamian myths are fundamentally written works. According to G.S. Kirk, classic Sumerian tales are “*elaborate and carefully composed narrative poems, which moreover make many excursions into ... the etymology of divine names.*”¹⁶ The semiotic derivation of names is deeply embedded in the art of cuneiform writing.

Significantly, many of the etymologies of Genesis cannot be directly understood from the Hebrew text. The derivation of Eve (*ḥwh*) from *mother of all who live* (Gen 3:20) is culturally lost. The link between Abraham (*ʿbrhm*) and the phrase *father of many nations* (Gen 17:5) is likewise a linguistic *non sequitur*. The mysterious name Moses (*mšh*) follows this pattern (Exod 2:10). Fortunately, we have a parallel text in cuneiform for comparison. The naming wordplays in the account of Sargon tell us what to look for in the birth story of Moses.

Cryptic Naming in the Birth Account of Sargon

Sargon (*šar-gi-na*) is named in the incipit of his own account.¹⁷ His naming phrase is comprised of a set of cuneiform double-entendres that encapsulates the plot of the story.

LUGAL.GI.NA, LUGAL dan-nu LUGAL a-ga-de₃^{ki} a-na-ku

Sargon, mighty king, king of Agade am I

The logogram LUGAL is read aloud as *šar* or *šarru* (*king*) in Akkadian. The homophone *šarru* signifies a reed basket. It also describes the flashing of a meteor in the night sky, interpreted as an omen.¹⁹ In Sumerian, *šar* can mean *to begin, to write, to insert, to enter* and *to drive*

¹⁶ Kirk, 1970, p. 115.

¹⁷ For context, Sargon II acknowledged using both numerological wordplays and pictographic word associations to render his name in official inscriptions (see Frahm, 2005, p. 48). It is clear that he encouraged his scribes to explore the esoteric significations of his name.

¹⁸ Hand copy (autograph) of the incipit by L.W. King, CT XIII, Plate 42, 1901.

¹⁹ *Šarru* may be written with the logogram SUR, the central component of the sign of the goddess Ištar who guided the ascent of Sargon. For the omenology of meteors, see Kingston Bjorkman, 1973.

away.^{20,21} **Gi** signifies *reed, to surround* and *boy*, while **na** (as **na₅**) is a *chest* or *box*. GI.NA (Sum. **genna**, Akk. *ginû*) refers to a young child. The homophone **ge₂₆-na** is an imperative form meaning *go*—implicitly in a *basket* (Sum. **bisag** = **ge₂₆**). The authoring scribe thus opens the story by using Sargon’s name to foretell the events to come.

When Mesopotamian scribes copied documents, they were required to faithfully reproduce the original signs. In *de novo* compositions however, orthographic decisions rested with the individual scribe. The author chose which signs to use, how and where to break up words, and whether to represent a given word logographically or syllabically or by combining both forms. Instead of following the convention of the ancient Legend of Sargon and recording the king’s name as *šar-ru-um-ki-in*, the author of the birth story appears to have created the details of the plot by parsing the ideographic meanings of potential alternate spellings.

The main plot of the older Sumerian account revolves around Sargon’s divinely aided “theft” of the throne of Ur-Zababa. According to the worldview preserved in the Sumerian King List, the kingship descended from heaven (ETCSL c.211). The author of the later Akkadian birth legend counteracts potential accusations of wrongful usurpation by “discovering” Sargon’s divine right to the kingship encoded in the form LUGAL.GI.NA. Given the overriding theme of legitimacy and right to rule, the following cluster of Sumerian meanings comes into play: **gi** can signify *judgment* and *to establish something as the property of someone*, while **na** functions as a suffix signifying either *that one* or the pronoun *he*. These properties are attached to **lugal** (*šarru*)—*king*.

The logogram GI.NA can also represent Akkadian ideas *kânu/kînu/kunnu*, meaning *to become permanent, firm, true*. Although Sargon’s older or better known name-forms *šarrûm-kîn*, *šarru-kên* and *šar-ukîn* also convey this idea, the logogram LUGAL.GI.NA incorporates the process of transforming an ostensibly illegitimate child into a king. LUGAL.GI encodes the *boy king* (Akk. *šarru ginû*) borne in a *reed basket* (*šarru qanû*). As a verb, *qanû* means *to acquire*, implying acquisition of the kingship (*šarru qanû*). The form *šarru kunnu* refers to a ritual object (the king in this case) correctly set in its ordained place.

²⁰ The language references drawn upon are the *CAD*, *CDA*, *ePSD*, *SL*, *CSL* and *Sefaria DDB*.

²¹ In an homage to the learned scholar, the scribe appears to make his intervention in the story metafictionally transparent by beginning with a pun on the word *beginning*—which we also see in the incipit of Genesis.

The basket containing the infant Sargon was discovered floating in the river by Akki the *water drawer* (^{lu}A.BAL). The sign A represents *mû*—meaning both *water* and *the cosmic order*. The sign BAL (signifying *to draw, recover*) also represents Akk. *enû* (f. *enītu*)—*to change* (including a dynasty), *to replace, substitute for, to reassign an omen to someone else*. Sargon’s mother was the royal *entu* priestess chosen by divination to bear the heir to the throne.²² However, her title is written *enetu* (*e-ni-tu₄*), signifying “*sin*” and “*changed order*”. She bore her child in secret and placed him in the water-proofed basket in the river, launching his journey to the throne. When Akki (^{lu}A.BAL) drew the boy from the water, he reassigned the kingship to him, thereby completing the task of his *entu* mother.

Polysemy in Narrative Context

Reconstructions of wordplay in ancient texts cannot be “proven” in an absolute sense. The vast potential of cuneiform to express different meanings (*polysemy*) may give the impression that attempts to decode ancient phrases amount to no more than a Rorschach test. Like patients projecting their psychological preoccupations upon an inkblot, interpreters may read a wide variety of hidden meanings into the signs. Hence, many Assyriologists view attempts to unravel such mysteries as a fool’s errand.

Nevertheless, there is a compelling argument to be made that cuneiform *oeuvres* that were conceptualized through polysemy cannot truly be understood without engaging the cryptic understorey of the text. If we read the ancient stories only as they appear on the surface, we consign ourselves to perceiving two dimensions where there are three, or to seeing only black and white where there is vivid color. Worse yet, we may miss the entire purpose of the ancient work.

With regard to naming wordplays, Jean Bottéro remarked that ancient scholar-scribes believed that the signs comprising a name (especially of a god or a hero) revealed the true nature of its bearer.¹⁰ These signs disclosed the bearer’s life task, personal destiny and place in the

²² Penelope Weadock (1975, pp. 127-128) cites 15 *entu* (NIN.DINGIR.RA) priestesses in the course of nearly two millennia. Each was the daughter of the ruling monarch (Akk. *šar kiššati*), who became her husband in temple fertility rites. The narrative implies that Sargon was not sired by Ur-Zababa, making him the product of a forbidden union with the *entu*.

cosmos. For the Akkadian scribes who composed or commented upon these texts, writing without polysemy was an oxymoron:

Due to the fact that ideography was identified with the idea of the graphic expression itself, it never occurred to ancient inventors and organizers of the script that henceforth one could ignore this basic ideography. (Jean Bottéro, *Mesopotamia*, p. 90, translated from French)

Modern scholars distinguish cuneiform signs voicing syllables (transcribed in lowercase) from signs representing ideas (transcribed in uppercase). Since every sign has both aural and visual values, the transcriber decides which sense fits the text. However, skilled scribes in antiquity worked both angles. Although ideography is widely acknowledged as an intrinsic part of Mesopotamian lore, Assyriologists primarily translate the syllabic sense of the signs, arbitrarily forcing a monolithic reading of the text. This removes key content from consideration. As explained by Scott Noegel,

Several devices can be employed simultaneously...each can have multiple functions...(Although) I distinguish those “wordplays” that operate only on a visual register from those that operate aurally...I acknowledge that some visual types work aurally and most aural types also operate visually. (Scott Noegel, 2021, p. 25)

A reader making a good faith effort to understand a cuneiform text as intended by the author cannot ignore this multivalency. The fear of being wrong is not a good enough reason to “ignore the basic ideography”. The objection that we simply cannot know what an ancient scribe was thinking is belied by the fact that he or she used signs to communicate in the first place. The ideographic stratum interrelates with the surface narrative. With regard to mundane texts (such as inventories of supplies), there may be no reason to suspect hidden meanings. However, the opposite holds true for myths and magical rites invoking the intervention of the gods. These genres intrinsically function on multiple levels of signification.

The scribes who embedded the *amāt niširti* (*hidden word*) in their works typically left clues. In the tale of Atrahasis, for example, the plain narrative recounts how the powerful god Enlil bullied the Divine Council into sending a flood to wipe out all life on earth. However, the

creator Ea secretly warned Atraḥasīs of the coming deluge. Ea doubly circumvented Enlil’s ban against alerting humans by addressing his warning to the wall of Atraḥasīs’ hut, which the flood hero overheard in a dream. The cognizant reader understands that Ea’s words are to be parsed for additional hidden speech. The carefully staged scene marks an X on the spot and says “Dig here!” Once the reader recognizes an alternate sign meaning that amplifies or refines the author’s theme, the discovery of a second and a third *amāt niṣirti* of a similar type strengthens the putative pattern. The key is narrative context.

The Hidden Guiding Hand Revealed Through Polysemy

The ancient use of polysemy was not confined to names. Sargon is introduced in his birth story with the adjective *dannu* (*mighty*), written with the signs DAN and NU (or simply DAN).² Each signifies additional Akkadian words related to the plot. DAN may be read as *ešqu*, connoting *fate*, *destiny* and *casting lots*.²³ The sign DAN reappears a few lines later in the verb used for casting the child into the river (*id-dan-ni*). NU (read as *ṭamû*) signals the magical *weaving* of strands. The homophone *tamû* connotes enchantment. The sign NU reappears in the locative term (*šak-nu*) for Sargon’s beginnings on the bank of the Euphrates. These cryptic elements are attached to LUGAL in the incipit. They reveal the undercurrent of fate guiding the future king to his destiny.

Sargon’s riverside “city” of origin is identified as *Azupiranu*—a place otherwise unattested in Mesopotamian geographical records. The name suggests a locale in which saffron (*azupīru*) may be found.²⁴ The logogram for the plant is 𒀠HAR.SAG (ḪUR.SAG), which happens to be the ideogram for the Mesopotamian river ordeal (*ḫuršānu*). In this judicial procedure, an accused person would leap into treacherous waters to establish his innocence (by survival) or reveal his guilt (by drowning).

In the Birth Legend, the infant Sargon survived being cast into the river. In the Legend of Sargon, the reigning king Ur-Zababa drowned in the river. The birth story thereby establishes

²³ Akk. *ešqu* connotes *surpassing*, *outstanding*, *strong*, *massive* (Sum. **rib**). However, it interchanges homophonically with a different *ešqu* (also written *išqu*, *isqu*) signifying *lot* and *fate* (equiv. to Heb. *goral*). It is related to the verb *ešequ*—*to draw an image*, *incise a relief*, *apportion lots*.

²⁴ Saffron was used in magical rituals to “*dispel evil magic*” (Maqlu V 31, CAD translation).

Sargon's innocence (from future regicide) by employing an inverse parallel to the revelation of Ur-Zababa's guilt in the older account. The audience is left to conclude that Sargon's ascent to the throne was the will of the gods.

We do not know how the birth story was presented to the public when it first appeared. Were they aware that it was a new composition? Was it brought out as a newly discovered ancient text? In either case, the audience could have deduced that the Sargon's birth account was reverse engineered from the story of the adult Sargon. Like a Hollywood prequel that is made after the successful establishment of a movie franchise, the birth narrative "knows" things it shouldn't. It demonstrates an awareness of a future that has not yet happened in the narrative—although the outcome is known to the audience.

Despite the teleological nature of the Sargonic birth narrative, the plot works. Instead of coming across as fake, the knowledge of future events serves to convey a powerful sense of prophecy that is enhanced by the scribe's choice of syllabic signs with cryptic ideographic meanings. Culturally speaking, this genre of story encapsulated the cosmology that undergirded the magical and religious rites of ancient Mesopotamia.²⁵ The symbols given by the gods encoded mankind's destiny (including the already known and the yet unknown). Hence, the cuneiform polysemy that animated the great myths also offered humans access to the cosmic patterns that framed existence.

After introducing Sargon in the incipit, the scribe who composed his birth story added additional layers of symbolic wordplay to the unfolding narrative. For instance, a foretelling of his future can be seen in the coating of bitumen applied to the basket by Sargon's *entu* mother. The normal Akkadian word for bitumen is *iṭṭû*, which is a homophone of *ittu*—an ominous sign of good or evil. In the context of the story, it alerts us to look closely at the logogram used by the scribe in place of the word. It signals that the substituted sign is an omen that discloses the events to come.

The author chose to represent *iṭṭû* with the logogram ESIR, which combines three signs: A.LAGAB x NUMUN (*WATER* + *ENCLOSURE containing SEED*). Intriguingly, the sign NUMUN is also ŠABALBAL. In Sumerian, it is written syllabically as ša₃-bal-bal, meaning *grandson* or *descendant*. Sargon's mother was the daughter of the king, making her child his grandson.²² Additionally, ša₃ bal means *to ponder*, while bal signifies *enemy, to tear down, to*

²⁵ See Reiner (1995, pp. 65-66) and Kramer and Maier (1989, p. 106) for links between myth and ritual.

change, to revolt. The *iṭṭû/ittu* sign was applied to KA₂—ostensibly the *hatch*, but cryptically representing the *city gate* as an administrative authority. In the setting of the legend of the rise of Mesopotamia’s greatest king, ŠABALBAL evokes the name of his predecessor, Ur-Zababa. In narrative context, the sealing of the basket by the priestess using *iṭṭû/ittu* foretells that the child contained within will lead a revolt against his grandfather’s regime.

Implicitly, the *iṭṭû* was also used to seal the infant’s *quppu*—reed basket. Irving Finkel identifies this term with a type of round, bitumen-coated reed boat used until recently in Iraq, called *quffa* in Arabic.²⁶ Sumerian lacks the syllable *qup*, which is an Akkadian pronunciation of the sign DU (*to go*). The sign also represents GIN (*to firmly* or *legally establish*) and GUB (*to install, to be assigned a task*). The final syllable *pu* (as BUR₁₂) is Akkadian *nasāḥu*—*to remove from office, to abolish a dynasty*.²⁷ *Nasāḥu* additionally means *to pull out from under a cover*, which fits the plain narrative of the boy’s discovery as well as conveying the sense of revealing what was concealed under the *iṭṭû*. These ideographic meanings of *quppu* repeat and ritually confirm the interpretation of the *boy-in-the-basket* omen.

The basket was consigned to the *river*, which the scribe chose to represent with the logogram ID₂ (which is A.LAGAB x ḪAL). The enclosed **ḫal** is another Sumerian word for *basket*. It also signifies *secret*. The ideogram for river can therefore be understood (in this context) as WATER + ENCLOSURE containing BASKET/SECRET. The author wrote ḪAL (in the first occurrence of ID₂) as an extra-wide sign that takes the form of DINGIR (*heaven, deity*)—making the child a secret of the gods. Although an analysis of oversized cuneiform signs in this text (and others like it) is beyond the purview of this discussion, it must be noted that this practice reappears as a technique used by Hebrew scribes for signaling hidden meanings. As we shall see, it is present in the defining adjective of the infant Moses.

Our discussion up this point lays the foundation for the Judean adoption of the wordplay prized by master scribes in Mesopotamia. Irving Finkel notes that the Birth Legend of Sargon was part of the Neo-Babylonian scribal curriculum, plausibly linking the young Judeans trained under Nebuchadnezzar (Dan 1:3-4) to the appearance of the Hebraic version of the story.²⁸ If (as

²⁶ Finkel, 2014, pp. 180-201.

²⁷ In some texts the final syllable is *pi*—which is also *geštu* (*to hear, to understand*). It is a variant that likewise fits the context of the *iṭṭû/ittu* omen.

²⁸ Finkel, 2014, pp. 335-339.

the Book of Daniel describes) these students subsequently rose to high office in Babylon, it means that they distinguished themselves as master scribes. As such, these elite Judeans were inculcated with the idea that the skillful manipulation of the signs could create powerful narrative spells to which the gods themselves were bound.¹³

The scribe who wrote the Mosaic adaptation of the Birth Legend of Sargon was obviously fascinated and motivated by this story. Why? If we consider the era in which the Akkadian Birth Legend tablet first appeared and if we evaluate its overriding theme of legitimate kingship in the light of contemporary political circumstances, we may reasonably conclude that it was written in support of Sargon II's *coup d'état*. This usurpation took place at the time of the fall of Samaria, the capital of the northern kingdom of Israel (c. 722 BC).

The Birth Legend inaugurated the dynasty of the Sargonid kings who reigned over Assyria's golden age. In the worldview of the Mesopotamian scholar-scribes, it was possible to change the future by (re)interpreting signs established by the gods.²⁹ From an initiate's perspective, the rise of this dynasty was set in motion by carefully crafted cuneiform ideography. I propose that the efficacy of this particular piece of cuneiform wordcraft "magic" (demonstrated by the success of the Sargonids who deported the inhabitants of Israel) convinced a classically educated deportee of its potential to drastically alter events in the temporal world.

Cryptic Naming in the Birth Account of Moses

One of the most striking features of the biblical narrative of Moses is that it never gives the Hebrew name of the leader of the nation. The name מֹשֶׁה (*mšh*, vowelized as *mōšēh* in the Masoretic Text) was bestowed by the Egyptian princess who discovered him floating in a basket in the river (Exod 2:1-10). Ostensibly, she coined the name in her own language—which according to the setting should be Egyptian. However, he was already three months old when she found him. Within the internal logic of the story, he would have had a Hebrew birth name—and a pre-Mosaic identity. These are missing from his biblical biography.

²⁹ This belief may be reciprocally rooted in *extispicy*—the reading of the liver (called the *tablet of the gods*) of a ram by a *barû* (*seer*). The *barû* chanted words to induce (or compel) the gods to change the signs spelling out the fate of the supplicant prior to revelation upon sacrifice (see Steinkeller, 2005).

The attribution of the Hebrew hero's sole appellation (*mšh*) to the linguistic invention of a foreign woman is shockingly unorthodox. The critical absence of a Hebrew name must therefore be understood as a narrative device pointing to a hidden object. To underscore this point, the Hebrew text states that Moses' birth mother "hid" him from Pharaoh (just as Sargon's mother hid him from Ur-Zababa). These anomalies signal that the true nature of Moses is concealed beneath the surface narrative, hidden from the reader as well as from Pharaoh.

The Hebrew narrative specifies that Moses' birth mother was from the sacerdotal tribe of Levi—and therefore an indigenous proxy for the original priestess. Before she hid him, she *saw* (in the sense of a *foretelling*) that he was *tôb* (*good*). According to the scribal guide *Ochlah W'ochlah*, certain Hebrew letters in the scriptures were required to be recorded with abnormal sizes to flag hidden meanings.³⁰ In this case, the scribes were instructed to write the adjective טוב (*tôb*) with an oversized ט (*t*). Its appearance signals a Hebrew "X marks the spot, dig here" narrative juncture. Some Talmudic commentators asserted that *tôb* was Moses' true name, positing that the adjective revealed the infant's aptitude for prophecy.³¹

Although the scribes and sages who shaped Judaism perceived the prophetic nature of Moses' birth mother's vision, the word *tôb* lacks a Hebrew semantic signification that compellingly rises to the stature of Moses' greatness or defines the nature of his task. Given that the name *mšh* replaces LUGAL.GI.NA (with its rich polysemy), we have every reason to expect a comparable construct—yet this is missing in the Hebrew text, just like his birth name. However, the Akkadian cognate of *tôb* is *tābu*, which may be written with the logogram SAG₈.³² This ideographic association links the Mosaic adaptation to its Sargonic template while launching the story of Israel's deliverance from captivity in a foreign land. SAG₈ is written with the same sign as DAN, repeating Sargon's defining adjective *dannu*—but with a clever twist.

Pharaoh feared a slave revolt, which prompted him to order that all Hebrew male infants be thrown into the river (Exod. 1:9-22). In Sumerian, the common word for slave is **sag**. Although it may appear contradictory, **sag** also signifies *first, foremost, leader*. Hence, the ideogram SAG₈ (expressing *tābu/good*) evokes the homophonic and contrasting ideas of *slave* and *pre-eminent*

³⁰ Frensdorff, 1864, #88. The oversized *tet* is not present in the Masoretic Text.

³¹ Sotah 12a:17

³² The normal logogram for *tābu* is DUG₃. The same sign is also Neo-Assyrian ŠAR₂.

leader (cf. SAG as Akk. *rēšu/rēštû*). Just as in the Birth Legend of Sargon, the sign also evokes *ešqu*, connoting *lot, fortune, fate* and *destiny*—including the *nature, power, special qualification* and *role* assigned by a deity.³³

To reiterate, the oversized *ṭ* recorded the Hebrew text of Moses' birth story marks a hidden meaning. When we trace this scribal signal flare to its literary launch point, it leads us to the language and script of the Sargonic temple. When the Hebrew adjective *ṭôb* is understood in terms of the ideography generated by its Akkadian cognate *ṭābu*, the narrative reason for veiling the identity of the infant Moses becomes apparent. In the light of this signal flare, we see that Moses' Levite birth mother hid him from Pharaoh when she foresaw that her son's destiny was to become the leader of the slave revolt. This is precisely the future the tyrant sought to preempt by murdering the infants. Just as in the story of Sargon, the author of the Mosaic version sets up a reversal of fate. The death by drowning decreed upon the Hebrew boys by Pharaoh ended up being his own doom.

The broad outlines of this poetic justice can be seen in the plain Hebrew text—and in many translations into other languages. However, the Levite woman's vision can only be understood via cuneiform polysemy. This example and others like it suggest the possibility that the birth story of Moses was originally composed with a stylus on a clay tablet and only later transcribed with the Hebrew/Aramaic consonantal script, written in ink upon a scroll. The scribal techniques employed by the Neo-Assyrian author of the source text were assimilated by the Hebraic reteller, who reproduced the constitutive polysemy along with the basic plot. His mimicry of this scribal art is part and parcel of his retelling of the Birth Legend of Sargon.

Paronomastic Constructs: Thematic Interlinkage of Alliterative Words

The reteller's cryptic subtext corresponds to the central theme of liberation from slavery that dominates the plain narrative of Moses. The compelling reason for this transformation of Sargon's story will be discussed in subsequent sections. For now, it is important to note that the writer cleverly employed the multilingual semantic field of *ṭôb* to set up a series of downstream cascading wordplays that develop and enhance the story. Once again, this pattern follows the

³³ Akk. *ešqu* (logogram DAN) interchanges here with its homonym *ešqu* (logogram ^(LÚ)GIŠ.ŠUB.BA).

Sargonic template. Intriguingly, the two letter root *tb* (in the syllabic form *ti₂-ib*) occurs in the Birth Legend of Sargon.³⁴

*Transliteration**Translation*

- | | |
|--|---|
| 7. id-dan-ni a-na [A].LAGAB x 𒀭HAL šá la e-le-e- ^r a ^r | 7. She (Sargon's mother) consigned me to the river from which I could not rise. |
| 8. iš-šá-an-ni A.LAGAB x 𒀭HAL a-na U[GU]
^r ak-ki ^{lu} A.BAL ú-bil-a[n-ni] | 8. The river carried me, to Akki the water-drawer it brought me. |
| 9. ^r ak-ki ^{lu} A.BAL i-na 𒀭i-i[b] d[a-l]i-šú l]u
ú-še-la-an-[ni] | 9. Akki the water-drawer by submerging his bucket raised me up. |

The syllables *ti₂-ib* represent the Akkadian word *tebû* (*to drown, sink, submerge*), which is the homophonic antonym of *tebû* (*to get up, arise, set out*). The *tb/tb* lexeme is used as a paronomastic wordplay to juxtapose the idea of the “submerged” hero as an infant with his rising up as future king. The scribe’s selection of syllabic signs ideographically enhances this narrative: the writing of *tebû* as *ti₂-ib* cryptically reveals the infant Sargon as the *hidden (ib) king* ($ti_2 = \text{šar}_2 \rightarrow \text{šar}$).³⁵ The homophone *tebû* (stative *ti-ib*) is the specific term used in Mesopotamian omen texts in the interpretation of signs portending rebellions.³⁶

The *tb/tb* omen pairing is reciprocal. The “submerging” of the infant boy is replaced by the drowning of the king. It evokes the river ordeal (𒀭HUR.SAG) underlying the riparian accounts of Sargon’s birth in *Azupiranu* (^u𒀭HUR.SAG) and Ur-Zababa’s death in the *river of blood* (Sum. **id₂ mud-še₃**, → Neo-Assyrian ID₂ 𒀭HU.ṬIB₂.ŠE₃). This intervention in *fate* (𒀭HU.ŠE) is faithfully reproduced in the story of Moses, who is called *ṭob* (*tābu/ṬIB₂*).

³⁴ 7th century BC tablet found in Ashurbanipal’s Library, Nineveh (Obverse, lines 7-9). Hand copy by L.W. King (1901, CT XIII, Plate 42). The Latin transcription and English translation are adapted from Lewis (1980). Missing signs are restored from other copies.

³⁵ Akk. *ti₂ ib* is also Sum. **dug₃ uraš** (*good secret*) and **šar₂ uraš** (~ *secret king*).

³⁶ For a typical example, see YOS 10 31 ii 15.

In the Neo-Babylonian era, *tebû* (*to rise up*) was written and pronounced as *tabû*—which is a homophone of *tābu*, the Akkadian form of Moses’ birth adjective. Significantly, *tabû* is expressed with the logogram ZI, which means *life* in Sumerian. It was sometimes written with the alternative logogram I.ZI.A, which can be read as an expression of the sum of its Sumerian parts: **i** (*to remove, take away, to bring out*), **zi** (*life*) and **a** (*water/nominative*). This is precisely the task that is assigned to Moses. The adjective *tôb/tābu* → *tabû* reveals that upon his birth, Moses’ priestess mother saw this future.

The Levite woman subsequently hid him in a floating basket, which is called a *tēbâh* (תבה) in the Hebrew account. This word lacks a known Hebrew root. It replaces *quppu* in the source account, indicating a deliberate scribal choice to substitute a different term. If we recall, the cuneiform sign representing *qup* is also GUB—*to be assigned* a task. We should therefore expect something similar in the Hebraic adaptation, but specific to Moses’ mission.³⁷ Not coincidentally, the only other appearance of the term *tēbâh* in the Bible is as the “ark” of Noah. This signals that both vessels serve the same purpose—to bring out life from water. We can easily spot some of the thematic links to the flood story. Righteous Noah was granted relief from the divine decree to submerge (*tebû*) all life. Likewise, Moses was spared from the mass drowning of Hebrew infants ordered by Pharaoh because he was good (*tābu*).

Bert Kouwenberg notes that Akkadian expressions or literary constructs often feature juxtapositions of different words sharing a similar root.³⁸ In this case, the placement of a child called *tb* (*tôb/tābu*) into *tb* (*tēbâh*) alerts us to a paronomastic construct. Moses’ defining goodness may be read as a number: TAB (*two*) + U (*ten*) forms TAB.U (*twelve* → Heb. *šē tēm-‘ešrêh*). The *tb/tb* construct cryptically foretells the rescue of the 12 tribes of Israel from the water—which is the task (*qup*/GUB) assigned to Moses.

Irving Finkel proposed that *tbh* (תבה) is a Hebraized form of Akkadian *tubbû*—a type of river boat.²⁶ To date, it is the only viable match of a known Mesopotamian watercraft to the unknown type of boat in the story of Moses. Although little is known of this craft, there is a kind of reed

³⁷ Note that **gub** is the central element of ^{LÚ}GUB.BA—*prophet*. Despite the substitution of another term, the signification of the source lexeme remains in play.

³⁸ N. J. C. Kouwenberg, 2021, p. 121. The term *figura etymologica* is sometimes used for this type of word pairing. With regard to the co-occurrence of Akkadian words with related forms or meanings, Kouwenberg suggests *paronomastic construct* as a better term.

called *ṭubû*. The homophone *ṭubbu* (or *ṭūbu*) means *goodness*, paronomastically connecting the vessel to Moses.

If this reconstruction of the original Akkadian term for Moses' watercraft is correct, we should expect that the author chose the name of this vessel only after careful consideration of the logographic values of its constituent syllabic signs. The word *ṭubbû* is written syllabically as *ṭu-bu-u₂*. The sign *ṭu* is AGA₃, which represents *crown* (Sum. **aga**, Akk. *agû*). It is also GIN₂, signifying *to bring low, to knock down* (Sum. **sug₅**). As noted previously in the analysis of Sargon's *qup-pu* boat, the sign PU/BU/BUR₁₂ can mean *to remove from office* or *to abolish a dynasty* (Akk. *nasāḫu*). The terminal *-u₂* potentially adds the connotation of *battle* and *defeat*. The vessels *quppu* and *ṭubbû* are very similar at an ideographic level.³⁹ Both predict the downfall of the tyrant king.

This brings us to the heart of the matter. In the source account, the *quppu* comes to Akki the water-drawer. Although he is treated as a character in the narrative, the sign AK is also AG—signifying *crown*. Ki is the cuneiform determinative for a geographic place. Thus, the vessel carrying the future king came to AG^{ki}, the *Place of the Crown*. However, AG is also the logogram for *nabû*—*to name, to call, to nominate for office*. When Akki lifted the infant boy out of the water, he simultaneously elevated him to the crown. This symbolism is foundational to the story. Although the water-drawer does not speak, his actions confirm Sargon as LUGAL.GI.NA, the true king declared in the incipit.

In the Hebraic reworking of Sargon's birth story, the boy in the basket becomes a prophet rather than a king. The vessel containing the future prophet came to Pharaoh's riverside palace—which is likewise the *Place of the Crown* (AG^{ki}). It is also the *Place of Nabû* (AG^{ki} = Akk. *nabû^{ki}*). In western Mesopotamia, the term *nābû* was associated with ascertaining fate.⁴⁰ The Hebrew cognate *nābî* (נָבִי) means *prophet*. Thus, the location on the bank of the river is the *Place of the Prophet* and the *Place of Naming*. In other words, the palace pier is the location of both Moses' naming and his call to office.

³⁹ If we take *tēbāh* as Hebraized *ṭubbû* (in keeping with Finkel's proposal), the watercraft is the narrative manifestation of the *ṭuppu* clay tablet carrying Moses (like Sargon) to his destiny (given that the phonemes *p* and *b* interchange in cuneiform).

⁴⁰ The office of the *nābû* is attested from Mari and Emar. The title may designate a diviner "named" by the gods as their messenger (see Durand, 1988, pp. 377-380 and Fleming, 1993, p. 188).

In Hebrew, this site is called *špâṭ ha-yʾōr* (שפת הַיַּאֲר) —the *bank of the canal* (Exod 2:3). In both Hebrew and Akkadian, the word for *bank* is also *lip*, associating the riverbank with speech. When read ideographically, the Akkadian cognate *šaptu* (*lip, rim, bank of a canal*) contains the constituent elements of this “Egyptian” scene. *Šaptu* is written with the logogram KA x NUN (MOUTH/COMMAND x PRINCE/MASTER). In Sumerian, the verb **nun** means *to rise up*. If *šaptu* is broken into two Akkadian words, the determinative pronoun *ša* (*of, with reference to, fit to be*) points to *pattu* (*canal*) and *pattû* (n. *reed chest/v. opened*). The expression *ša patti* (*on the border of*) is written with the logogram ZAG—which is the sign for *mišru*, a variant form of Mušri—Egypt.⁴¹

The same bank of the river is the setting of Moses’ eventual face-to-face confrontation with Pharaoh (Exod. 7:15-20). In this encounter, the Hebrew leader demanded that his people be set free. Once again, a deeply relevant cuneiform semantic field emerges when Hebrew *špâṭ* is taken as a translation from Akkadian. *Šapāṭu* means *to inform strictly, to reprimand and to give judgment, exercise authority* (~ Heb. לַשְׁפֹּט). *Šapattu* (*šabattu*) is the 15th day of the month. It is the night of the full moon in the standardized Babylonian lunar calendar—and the night of Israel’s future departure from Egypt. The number 15 can be denoted with the logogram ZAG—which again is *mišru*/Egypt.

If we overlay the Mosaic and Sargonic birth accounts and read them as a composite text, Pharaoh’s daughter takes the place of Akki, the water-drawer who discovers Sargon in the floating basket. She gave the infant the name *mšh*—which she derives from her act of drawing him from the water. Pharaoh’s daughter thus named Moses in the exact narrative location of AG^{ki} (*Place of Naming/Place of the Prophet/Place of the Crown*) in the source text. Viewed without prejudice, this precise correspondence informs us that the composer of the birth story of Moses worked directly from the tablet of Birth Legend of Sargon. Concomitantly, it shows that the author was an accomplished cuneiform scribe.

In Exodus, the role of Sargon’s *entu* priestess mother is played by Moses’ Levite birth mother. The role of Akki the water-drawer is played by the daughter of Pharaoh. In Mesopotamia, the office of the *entu rabû* (*high priestess*) was always held by a daughter of the king.²² The birth story of Moses splits the princess-priestess role in two: the Levite woman and

⁴¹ Tel Amarna 289:34 (cuneiform correspondence from Jerusalem) records “Egypt” as ^{mātu}*mi-iš-ri^{ki}*.

the king's daughter. One placed the boy in the river, the other (like Akki) took him out. This reciprocity reverberates through the Exodus account. It is deeply embedded in the paronomastic *tb/tb* series.

This ideographic sequence is *set in motion* (Akk. *tabû*) when the Levite birth mother of the chosen child saw that he was *tôb* (Akk. *tābu*). The prophetic vision and actions of the Levitess are completed by Pharaoh's daughter, who takes the boy out of the river and names him. She derives the child's name from this act, saying *for from the water I drew him* (→ I.ZI.A → *tabû*). The Levitess and the princess thus combine to carry out the ritual function of the *entu* as the declarer of destiny.⁴² This mirroring indicates that *tābu* belongs to the first part of Moses' naming, which is then completed by the second *entu*.⁴³

The Completion of Moses' Naming

The birth story of Moses credits Pharaoh's daughter with coining a unique personal name derived from the circumstances in which she discovered him. The name should therefore be Egyptian, yet the narrative confusingly provides a Hebrew etymology. Scholars have long suspected this etymology as an alibi meant to obscure an original Egyptian name by removing the theophoric element of his name (e.g. Ra, Thoth) and developing a cover story for the residual suffix *-mose* (meaning *born of*).⁴⁴ However, this assumes the existence of a historical 2nd millennium Egyptian Moses. As noted previously, there is no material evidence of the name Moses from before the exile, nor does the archaeological record support the public practice of the Mosaic Law in antiquity.

Although traditionalists will instinctively reject the idea of the emergence of Moses as a cultural hero after the Babylonian exile, the Hebrew scriptures themselves acknowledge that the nation did not know the words of the Torah Scroll until very late in its history. This ignorance extends from the era of the Judges before the rise of the monarchy (Jdg 17:5-6) to the reigns of

⁴² According to Albert Clay, "*the entu were devoted to the practice of magic*"—especially *divination* (1915, YOS I 45, p. 68).

⁴³ In conjugated form, *tabû* (*tebû*) may introduce direct speech, identifying the ensuing signs as the declaration of the prior-named person. This links the first woman (as *seer*) to the second (as *speaker*).

⁴⁴ Carroll, 1985, p. 775.

the last kings of Judah five centuries years later (2 Kgs 22:8-11). The Mosaic Law remained unknown to the common people at least 90 years after the exiles were permitted to return from Babylon (Neh 8:1-9).⁶ We may add the caveat that some taboos (such as eating pork) were intrinsic to the ancestral culture of the ruminant-herding nomadic tribes that settled the hill country of Canaan in mid-to-late 2nd millennium BC—despite their later attribution to Moses. The possibility that Moses and the full Mosaic Law existed in antiquity while remaining obscure for centuries must be considered extremely unlikely.

The fact that Moses' birth account derives from a story written in Akkadian tells us to look to the literary language of Mesopotamia to understand the name and the identity given to him by the princess in the narrative. Although the geographic setting of Moses' birth is Egypt, its linguistic context is Mesopotamian. This jarring contradiction has somehow been disregarded or passed over during the 125 years since the Birth Legend of Sargon was published.⁴⁵ If the reader sets aside assumptions of Egyptian language, the etymological anchoring of Moses' naming in the bilingual Akkadian-Sumerian cuneiform idiolect leaps out.

Readers should keep in mind that Hebrew *mšh* (משח) is written consonantly. More than a thousand years after the Babylonian exile, the Masoretic scribes added vowel points to sound the prophet's name out as *mōšēh* (מֹשֶׁה). However, a lexeme derived from Akkadian would originally have been voiced with the vowel "u" instead of "o", forming the initial syllable *mu* instead of *mo*. With this simple vowel transposition, the immediate meaning of the etymology of *mšh* is apparent. The naming statement *from the water I drew him* plays upon Akkadian *mû* (*water*) and Sumerian **mu** (*son, name, to give a name*). The sign MU represents Akkadian *nīšu* (or *nēšu*), which describes the act of *lifting* or *raising*.

Although the opening **mu**/*mû*/MU wordplay precisely fits the scene of the infant drawn from the river, the narrator had far grander plans in mind for his hero. *Nīšu* (*nēšu*) has the alternate meaning of *people*. The word also signifies *relatives* and may refer to members of a specific family. The homophone *nēšu* means *to live* and *to revive*. At this point readers should recall Benjamin Foster's insight into the composition of a cuneiform epic: "*For the poet, the name, properly understood, discloses the significance of the created thing.*"¹¹

⁴⁵ Most of this scholarship falls under the framework of Source Critical Theory, which ironically ignores known Mesopotamian sources in favor of hypothetical Hebrew oral and written traditions.

If Hebrew *mšh* (משח) is understood as a consonantal transcription of syllabic cuneiform, *mu* is the prefix and initial symbolic element of the defining name coined for him. The stem *šh* comprising the semantic core of his name can then be reconstructed by syllabic expansion to Akkadian *šēḫu*—which means *ecstatic* or *prophet*.⁴⁶ Grammatically, *mušēḫu* signifies *one who prophesies*.⁴⁷ The sign MU is also IA₅, making it a theophoric element forming the name *Prophet of Yah* (or *Ea*). Moses' mission emerges from the synergy of constituent homophonic wordplays: he is the *prophet who revives the people* MU (*nēšū/nêšū*) *šēḫu*.⁴⁸ Critically, his name was bestowed at the *Place of the Naming/Place of the Prophet* (Akki → AG^{ki} → Nabû^{ki}) in the composite text.

At first impression, the word *šēḫu* may strike readers as unnatural or too obscure to be associated with “Moses”. Such discomfiture manifests disconnection from the source, revealing the great gulf between the familiar biblical account today and the time, place, language, culture and cosmological context of its composition. In fact, the significance of the *šēḫu* and his office would have been very clear to an audience in Neo-Babylon. The *šēḫu* was not just any prophet—he was the most powerful practitioner of magic in the land.

The 12-day long national festival of Babylon (the Akītu) featured a parade in which a man called *ša šehi* (lit. *imbued with divine spirit*) rode in a chariot drawn by horses.⁴⁹ The team was costumed as the fearsome mythological monster, ^dZû.⁵⁰ In the heroic primeval epoch celebrated in Mesopotamian legends, Lord Zû seized control of fate by stealing the Tablet of Destinies from the gods. After a great battle, the tablet was retrieved by the warrior god Ninurta, who subsequently tried to abscond with it. The wise god Ea used his magic to regain possession of

⁴⁶ More commonly written *šēḫānu*, but also recorded as *ša šehi*.

⁴⁷ *Mušēḫu* may also be read as MU-*šēḫu* (*son of the prophet*). The Heb. expression *b^{nē} ha-n^ebiyīm* (*sons of the prophets*) is well-attested in the Hebrew scriptures as a collective term for prophets as a guild.

⁴⁸ MU-*šēḫu* also signifies the *prophet of the line of the tablet*, adding the metafictional disclosure that *mušēḫu* was drawn forth from the written word.

⁴⁹ For the cuneiform text describing the parade, see Ebeling, 1920 (KAR) 307: 25-27. For transcription and translation, see Ebeling, 1931 (TuL), p. 33.

⁵⁰ This divine bird (Zû, Anzû or Lord Zû) appears in multiple Sumerian myths. His defeat by Ninurta is depicted in many Mesopotamian cylinder seals. For the account of Zû's theft of the Tablet of Destinies, see Scheil (1938) and Kramer and Maier (1989, pp. 140-142, 84-86).

destiny and put order back in the cosmos. In the Akītu parade, the *šēhu* stood next to the king of Babylon—the emperor of all the lands—who was dressed as Ninurta. The mage held the tongues of Zû in his hands, using them as reins to control the beast. All the eyes of the great throng that traveled to the magnificent capital city of the Babylonian Empire for the Akītu holiday were fixed upon the two men in the chariot.

This dramatic performance mirrored the ancient cosmic model. Although the king outranked the mage in the political order, the mythological iconography of the scene reversed their standing. Implicitly, the *ša šēhi* was imbued with the spirit of Ea. Since Ea had defeated Ninurta to take back the power of the universe, the mage held mastery over the king. This cultural context gives us a sense of the persona and power of the *šēhu* and his appeal to the captive Hebrew nation. He symbolically held the reins of fate in his hands, giving him the power to bend the cosmic order to his will.

The scene provides us with a tangible source of inspiration for a mighty leader capable of wresting the nation’s stolen destiny from a terrifying foe. The *ša šēhi* publically participated in the reenactment of a Babylonian myth, yet he was a flesh and blood man. The crowds lining the parade route saw both the man (presumably a renowned practitioner of the magical arts) and the mythological role he played. In the eyes of the Hebrew exiles watching the grand spectacle, the *šēhu* had the stature to stand alongside the king himself—whom he magically outranked. The scene gives us a framework for reconciling the biblical sense of Moses as a real person with his literary origin as a figure drawn from the waters of myth.

Šēhu (or *šēhānu*) is written with the logogram A₂.KAM, which ideographically represents an ecstatic in the *grasp* (**kam**) of a *power* (**a₂**). Reciprocally, the *šēhu* grasped *power* with his *arm* (**a₂**). In the context of the public reenactment of the recovery of the Tablet of Destinies from Zû, the ideogram A₂.KAM also draws upon **kam₃** (signifying both *tablet* and *to alter, to overturn*). The *ša šēhi* had the competency to wield the Tablet of Destinies in his hand.⁵¹ This Akītu scene suggests the roots of the Hebraic conception of *mšh* holding the talismanic twin tablets (Akk. *mašmaš*) inscribed by the finger of “Elohim” (Exod 31:18).⁵²

⁵¹ This power came from Ea, who laid out the plan for defeating Zû at the request of the distraught gods of the divine council. In the Legend of Zû (VAT 8017, obv. 31-35), Ea is called *master of hearing* (i.e. knowledge → ZU) and the *ašipu* of ZU.AB, making him the paronomastic master of ZÛ (and the tablet).

⁵² The tablets were specifically made of stone (Heb. *ʿeben*, Akk. *abnu* → NA₄). This sign is also IA₄.

In the context of the Akītu parade, a Hebrew-speaking scribe educated in the hidden lore of the cuneiform scholars (*niširti ummâni*) could not have missed the linguistic link between KAM (QAM₂) in A₂.KAM and Hebrew *qam* (קָם)—the past tense of the verb *arise*. In fact, *qam* is the specific verb used in the Hebrew scriptures to mark the inauguration of a prophet’s career (see Deu 18:15, Jer 29:15, Amos 2:11). Whether this usage precedes or (more likely) postdates the Babylonian exile, it is exemplified in the life of Israel’s iconic leader.

Moses’ epitaph encapsulates the essence of the great Babylonian *šēhu* (A₂.KAM).⁵³ It is recorded as the last verse of Deuteronomy, the final book of the Pentateuch. In synagogues today, the annual liturgical cycle of the Torah scroll concludes with the reading of this tribute: “*There arose (qam) not a prophet again in Israel like Moses*” who performed “*great deeds of power*” with his “*mighty hand*” (Deu 34:10-12).

Although Moses became the Hebrew cultural archetype of the venerable, wise and magisterial leader, the defining property of his unique power is obscured in the consonantal Hebrew text. Instead, it is encoded in the cuneiform signs that were later transcribed as *mšh*. If syllabic *še-hu* is read as the logogram ŠE.ĤU, the signs form the logogram for *fate* (Sum. **nam** → ĤU.ŠE), but in reversed order. Symbolically, MU.ŠE.ĤU is the *son* born to reverse the nation’s fate of slavery in a foreign land.⁵⁴

Overturning Fate: From Heaven to Earth

The considerable effort exerted by the authoring scribe to derive the name *mšh* from the matrix of the Birth Legend of Sargon underscores the importance of the Babylonian *šēhu*. It warrants a closer look at the cosmological role of the enigmatic beast-master of the Akītu festival. We know that the *ša šehi* rode in the king’s chariot and held the “*tongues*” of Zû in his hands. The logogram for *tongue* (EME) is comprised of the sign for *mouth* (KA) containing the sign for the *divine rules and instructions* (ME). In both symbol and deed, the dramatic imagery of the *šēhu* gripping Zû’s power of speech conveys mastery of cosmic authority.

⁵³ Since the logogram A represents *mû*, a reading of A₂.KAM as A.KAM suggests the idea of the Hebraic *šēhu* arising from *water*, which is also the *cosmic order*.

⁵⁴ The anagram MU.ĤU.ŠE suggests *Son who Hears the Decree of Heaven*: ĤU.ŠE represents Akk. *šamu* (to fix a decree), while the homophone *šamû* (AN) means *heaven* and *to hear* (*šamû* as ŠE.GA).

This meaning is evident from another aspect of this public drama. The chariot bore the threshold of the temple of the god Enmešarra, a primordial deity from a different lineage of myths—stories that likewise concern the control of destiny. ^dEn-me-šar-ra means *Lord of All the Me* in Sumerian. In various versions of the myth, the gods Enlil, Ninurta or Marduk fought him for the right to decide fate. The display of Enmešarra’s threshold in the parade constituted a public demonstration of the cosmic authority wielded by the king of Babylon. Acting in the role of Ninurta/Marduk, the king controlled destiny on behalf of his nation. However, the presence of a powerful magical practitioner at his side discloses that the king required the help of a human specialist to secure this control. For the cheering crowds, the passage of their king and their mage bearing these ritual symbols offered reassurance that their leaders possessed the means to assure the nation’s future.

The 6th century presence of watching Judean exiles offers a historical window of opportunity for the emergence of an equivalent Hebrew concept. It suggests that this grand Babylonian display of primeval power held in the hands of one man captured the imagination of the future author of the account of Moses. The latent potential of the *šēhu* to reverse the fate of his own people provides a compelling reason for the conceptualization of a Hebraic retelling. The narrative of the nation’s Exodus from Egypt that follows from Moses’ birth draws upon the same cluster of myths that were reenacted during the 12 days of the Akītu.

Chief among these was the Enuma Elish—the literary epic of Babylon that was read aloud during the national festival. Like the myths of Zû and Enmešarra, its central subject is the control of fate. The narrative recounts Marduk’s cleaving of the primordial sea serpent Tiāmat, who possessed the Tablet of Destinies. Marduk was the patron god of Babylon. His seizure of the tablet resulted in the rise of his nation to dominion. Marduk’s cosmological deed (in the heavenly realm) was mirrored in the temporal world (on earth) by the ascent of Babylon to the head of the nations. The parade featuring the defeated Zû and the threshold of Enmešarra was integrated into the Akītu celebration of Marduk’s seizure of the tablet.

This conceptual cluster appears in the writings of the exiles of Judah. The prophet Isaiah cited the primordial sea serpent (Heb. *tannîn*) in a double metaphor representing the enslaving sea of the exile and the ensorcelling power of evil destiny. He pleaded with the “*arm of Yahweh*” to split the *tannîn* to form a pathway of dry land through which the exiles might return to Zion (Isa 51:9-11, cf. 35:7-10). The narrative setting of these words and their historical

context places the prophet among the exiles of Judah, making him the second of three scribes who wrote under the same sobriquet.⁵⁵ The key point is that Isaiah envisioned the rescue of his nation from Babylon (see Isa 46:1-3, 13) in terms of the cosmic battle against the primeval sea-serpent that controlled fate.⁵⁶

The prophet Jeremiah (c. 650-570 BC) used the same metaphor while making a direct allegorical application. Jeremiah identified the *tannîn* as the king of Babylon who “swallowed” the nation (Jer 51:34). At this early stage of the exile, Jeremiah (who was not deported to Babylon) openly named Nebuchadnezzar as the sea serpent. Writing later, Deutero-Isaiah veils the monster’s identity as well as the name of the rescuing entity.⁵⁶ His appeal for divine deliverance in the present/future is later recalled (by Trito-Isaiah) as a *fait accompli* credited to Moses (Isa 63:11-132). These disclosures attest to a Hebraic fusion of myth and contemporary circumstances.

The convergence of destiny myths in the Babylonian Akītu festival served to realign temporal events by reworking the ancient cosmic order. The tales of Tiāmat, Zû and Enmešarra were recast and reenacted for the purpose of aiding Babylon. The same pattern is present in the biblical accounts of Genesis/Exodus. The Mesopotamian myths of Dilmun, Atraḫasīs and Sargon are retold as Eden and exile, the Ark and the Flood, the basket and Moses.⁵⁷ These distinct stories are narratively linked together to call into being a remnant of the nation that will survive the exile and return to Zion. The sequence of retold myths in Genesis culminates in the

⁵⁵ Although Isaiah is archaeologically attested in late-7th century Jerusalem (see Mazar, 2018, pp. 180-182), the Book of Isaiah engages geopolitical events across two centuries—not just as prophesy, but as lived experience (see Isa 64:9-11). Most biblical scholars attribute the middle chapters of his eponymous book to an exilic scribe (Deutero-Isaiah), while the later chapters are attributed to an early post-exilic writer (Trito-Isaiah).

⁵⁶ As shown by Hutton (2007), Deutero-Isaiah employs specific ideas and vocabulary drawn from the myth of Anat’s slaying of the *tannîn* (KTU 1.3 from Ugarit). The prophet unmistakably calls upon a female deity, asking “*Are you not she who hewed Yam (Sea)?*” (Isa 51:10). Although this myth is from the Levant, the scribe adds the serpent pseudonym רהב (*rhb*)—possibly a syllabic spelling of Akk. *ra’ābu* (*rahābu*) connoting *divine wrath*. When understood as the sum of its parts, RA represents *inundation* (*riḫīštu*) and *to strike* (*maḫāšu*), while A (*mû*) is *water* and BU is the ancient ideogram for *serpent*.

⁵⁷ This link between Mesopotamian myth and the early stories of the Bible was recognized by George Smith (*Chaldean Genesis*, 1876) when he translated the newly discovered tablets.

ancient tale of the slaying of the sea serpent (in Exodus), which is recast as Moses' splitting of Yam Suph.⁵⁸ The cleaving of the personified sea enabled the exiles to return to their ancestral homeland, just as described by Isaiah.

The series of symbolic accounts in Genesis/Exodus ritually invokes the realignment of temporal events. It is a powerful biblical parallel to the dramatic representations of the 12-day Akītu festival. Both dramas required a *šēhu* capable of grasping the Tablet of Destinies in his hand and controlling the cosmic forces. In Akkadian thought, *mû* represents *the cosmic order* as well as *water*. *Mû* is the matrix from which Moses was drawn. It is also the matrix from which the enslaved nation was drawn. His birth story signals that the future leader was called to change the fate of his people. The narrative replacement of his birth name with the act of drawing him from the water underscores his conceptual essence as *mû šēhu*.

Despite being imbued with esoteric powers from infancy, the future prophet and leader was born into slavery in a foreign land. His task (both within the narrative and in real-world application) was to free his nation from a life of hard labor and servitude and bring them back to their homeland. The scribe brought Moses forth from the cosmic order—and transferred him to the temporal realm. Concomitantly, the author transformed myth into political allegory. Following the methods of his erstwhile Mesopotamian masters, the scribe manipulated words and symbols to achieve this transformation.

Paradigm Shifts

As remarked in the introduction, most literary comparisons of the Mosaic and Sargonic origin accounts digress into discussions of heroic folklore or the foundling child myth.² Although this scholarly rubric presents itself as an erudite unifying thesis, the effort to universalize human ideas ignores the time, place, circumstances, motives and individuality of the creators—and contemporary politics. The birth story of Sargon the Great was most likely composed on behalf of Sargon II, who seized the throne from Shalmaneser V in 722 BC. This conclusion is based

⁵⁸ Although ים סוף is often translated as *Sea of Reeds*, סוף (*sûp*) also means *to consume, come to an end, perish, conclude, fulfill*. In allegorical context, the sea reflects the meanings of Akk. *suppû*: *to abduct* (slaves), *to be taken away* and *to pray* or *to supplicate* a deity.

upon the shared name Sargon, the central motif of the divine right to rule and its correspondence to a political event that occurred during the era in which the work first appeared. If this *coup d'état* provided the motivation for adding a prequel to the Legend of Sargon, it informs us that the Mesopotamian literary source of Moses' birth account had a subversive dimension. It is a motivating feature that warrants a correspondingly close look in the Hebraic adaptation of the story.

In a welcome departure from the universalizing formula taught by modern scholars of ancient myths, Eckart Otto noted that the vocabulary and phraseology of the Birth Legend of Sargon story gives it a Neo-Assyrian time stamp.⁵⁹ Otto then recognized that the dependence of the birth story of Moses upon this source imposes an absolute historical time boundary: the literary beginning of Moses cannot predate the Neo-Assyrian era. Moreover, this reality concomitantly informs us that the Egyptian setting of Moses cannot be historical, but must instead be a retrospective allegorical substitution.

Otto concluded that the Mosaic theme of liberation was a Judean response to 7th century Neo-Assyrian imperialism with its imposition of *corvée* labor upon the conquered peoples:

The author ... of the Exodus of Moses projects the forced labor of the neo-Assyrian hegemonic power onto the fictitious situation of Israel in Egypt and in this way makes the (meaning of the) events at the time of Moses in Egypt transparent to the audience for Moses' exodus tales in the 7th century BC. Eckart Otto (*Die Geiburt des Mose*, p. 25, translated from German)

Otto identifies multiple passages elsewhere in the Hebrew Bible that draw upon Neo-Assyrian oracles and legal documents. Nevertheless, his *terminus ad quem* is too early. Otto's conclusions require Judean mastery of cuneiform at a time (the 7th century BC) and a place (Jerusalem) for which we have no archaeological evidence for this level of foreign cultural adoption and access to cuneiform source documents. Based on the available epigraphic data, Judeans used the Old Hebrew script for official inscriptions and for all internal correspondence (i.e. non-diplomatic) until the Babylonian conquest.

⁵⁹ Otto (2009, p. 24) cites the presence of words and formulaic phrases in the Birth Legend of Sargon that only occur in Neo-Assyrian literature.

In contrast, we have extensive evidence that communities of Judean deportees in 6th century Babylonia adopted Akkadian cuneiform as their medium for keeping written records.⁶⁰ In fact, the transition from the traditional Judean script to cuneiform in Babylonia can be seen in Akkadian tablets labeled on their spines with the name of their owner in Old Hebrew.⁶¹ The incorporation of Neo-Assyrian material only imposes the requirement that the relevant Hebrew texts cannot predate them. Archived Neo-Assyrian tablets were accessible to 6th century Judean scribes educated in Babylon and employed in the royal service (see Dan 1:3-4, 2:48-49). Some of these works were even part of the Neo-Babylonian school curriculum.²⁸

The Hebraic retelling of the Birth Legend of Sargon makes significant changes that align with 6th century developments—especially the restoration of the empire of the empire by King Nabonidus (r. 556-539 BC) after a lapse of 500 years. Although the *entu* plays a critical part in the story of Sargon, her visible role is subtle. The Neo-Assyrian author clearly knew of this priestesshood and understood the dynastic implications of an illicit *entu* pregnancy. Nevertheless, the author did not see the need for her continued presence in the narrative. In contrast, the role of the *entu* is augmented in the Hebraic adaptation by transforming the water-drawer Akki into Pharaoh's daughter.⁶²

This princess gave Moses the only name by which he is known—the name that Yahweh himself accepted and used (Exod 3:4). The narrative choice to place the declaration of his enigmatic name in the mouth of a foreign princess is shocking—more so now than ever, given Moses' cultural stature as the pivotal figure of Hebrew history and religion. Pharaoh's daughter merits the full attention of anyone wishing to understand the story. When Pharaoh sought to kill the Hebrew males who might one day rise up in rebellion, his own daughter saved the one child who was destined to lead this revolt. She is therefore the person who set Moses on the revolutionary path of destroying her father the king.

⁶⁰ See Pearce and Wunsch, 2014.

⁶¹ Vukosavovic, 2015, p. 105.

⁶² Although Otto (2009, p. 24) makes a connection between the unnamed *entu* in the Birth Legend and Enheduanna (the real-life 23rd century *entu* daughter of Sargon the Great), she lacks a 7th century context. The *entu* plays no role in the Neo-Assyrian socio-political allegory that Otto reconstructs from the Hebrew text.

Intriguingly, we find out in a genealogical postscript that this foreign princess joined the tribe of Judah during the nation's exodus from "Egypt" (1 Chr 4:18). This anecdote cryptically discloses that Pharaoh's daughter was "taken by mered" (מרד). Although the genealogical format lulls the reader into assuming that *mered* is the name of a biological ancestor, the word means *rebellion*. In context of the Exodus, it alludes to her subversive role in Egypt.⁶³ She is renamed *bat-yah* (*daughter of Yah*), which is juxtaposed with *bat-par'ōh* (*daughter of Pharaoh*). In parallel, her change of allegiance is recognized by giving her the epithet *ha-y^hhudîyâh* (*the Jewess*).⁶⁴

The plot twist of Pharaoh's daughter joining the tribe of Judah as it left Egypt adds critical information that is missing from the main story. The genealogy reveals that the princess joined the slave revolt. The statement that she was "taken by mered" precisely fits this context. Tellingly, the chronicler identifies the rebellion with Judah.⁶⁴ The dependence of the main story upon a Neo-Assyrian literary model leaves us with two classification options: either it is fiction or it is allegory. The addition of this remarkable genealogical entry to the tale of Pharaoh's daughter points to the latter.

The appearance of the Hebrew word *mered* (*rebellion*) in the genealogical record triangulates with the underlying political theme of the birth stories of Moses and Sargon. The name *mušēḫu* encodes future insurrection—just like the title LUGAL.GI.NA. The interchangeability of the sibilants *s* and *š* gives *sēḫu* (*to rise up and revolt*) in place of *šēḫu*. By extension, the form *museḫû* refers to *one who foments rebellion*. The paronomastic pairing of *prophet* (*šēḫu*) and *rebel* (*sēḫu*) completes the foretelling of Moses' birth mother, who "saw" that the child was *ṭob* (Akk. *ṭābu* → *tabû*—*to rise up in rebellion*). His adoptive mother then named (*nabû*) him as *šēḫu* (= *nābû*) in the Place of Nabû (AG^{ki}), making him the *nābi'u* (*one who rises and revolts*) who would lead his people to freedom.

⁶³ The use of names as metaphors is a characteristic of the Hebrew scriptures. For instance, the sons of Zeruah (*trouble sent by Yah*) repeatedly brought divine guilt upon the House of David (see 2 Sam 2:18-26, 3:26-29, 16:8-10, 1 Chr 27:24). We never meet Zeruah herself, but see her only through her troublesome sons.

⁶⁴ Her entry into the genealogy of Judah (as opposed to Levi, the tribe of Moses whom she adopted) hints at the allegorical nature of the anecdote. She is anachronously called *the Jewess* (the only occurrence of this term in the Hebrew Bible), affiliating her with the descendants of the exiles.

Given the underlying Akkadian vocabulary of Moses' birth story and its Mesopotamian source, Pharaoh's daughter is merely costumed as an Egyptian on the narrative stage. Off stage, she is a Mesopotamian *entu*. Following ancient tradition, the *entu rabû* was chosen from among the daughters of the ruling monarch of the epoch. Hence, if this story is indeed an allegorical play upon real events, the genealogical entry for "Pharaoh's daughter" intimates that she joined a historical rebellion against her father—not in Egypt, but in the Place of Nabû, where she enters the narrative. The fact that the fate of the princess is disclosed in a late postscript indicates that something changed between the writing of the main story and the recording of this addendum. It suggests that what began as a secret scribal hope for overturning Judah's fate later became a successful real-world political intrigue.

Egypt as Babylon

If we set aside the longstanding assumption that מצרים (*miṣrāyīm*, Akk. *muṣri*, *miṣrum*) is geographical Egypt, the underlying motivation for the Judean adaptation of the Sargonic account comes into focus.⁴¹ The 1st millennium Mesopotamian literary source of Moses together with the late date of emergence of Mosaic practices in the popular culture signal that the location of the Exodus is figurative. When the narrative cues are analyzed within these time limits, it becomes apparent that biblical slavery in "Egypt" in antiquity is a metaphor for contemporary slavery in 6th century Neo-Babylon.

This inference is supported by hints that biblical "Egypt" refers to two different places, depending on context—as suggested by the Hebrew suffix *-ayim*.⁶⁵ "Egypt" always appears in the dual form *miṣrayim*. The allusion to a pair is usually understood to connote Upper and Lower Egypts, which existed as separate kingdoms until they were united under one crown.⁶⁶ However, this duality is not merely a nomenclatural tradition. Multiple biblical anecdotes associate symbolic pairs with Israel's departure from Egypt (see 2 Chr 5:10, 1 Kgs 12:28, Jos 2:1-10).

⁶⁵ Nadav Na'aman argues that *-ayim/n* is a locative suffix in place names (2008, pp. 2-3). However, the suffix is used for twin towns (e.g. Kibṣayim, Jos 21:22) and for particular places that were believed to have divine doppelgangers (e.g. Maḥanayim, Gen 32:1-2).

⁶⁶ Leprohom, 2013, p. 15.

These allusions signal a numinous link between the land of captivity, the two tablets of Moses, the divided kingdom of Israel and the future miraculous return of the unified nation from exile (see Hos 1:11). Intriguingly, the sign MAŠ (*half, twin*) underlies Mesopotamian concepts of conjuration and exorcism (*mašmašūtu*). Israel’s escape from Egypt required the sea to be split in two on the night of the 21st of Nisan (Exod 12:17-18, 14:21)—under the waning half moon.⁶⁷ In the cuneiform lexical series Ea A Nâqu, Akkadian *mi-iš-rum* is paired with **ma-aš₂ MAŠ** (A I/6:90).⁴¹ Sumerian **ma aš₂** signifies *to bind a curse*. Assuming that the Judean scribes consulted this compendium, they assimilated **ma aš₂ MAŠ** not only as a ritual invocation of their escape from *mīšrum*, but also to bind the cursed halves of Israel together.^{68,69}

If we keep in mind the mid-1st millennium *terminus a quo* for literary Moses, there is no Israelite slavery in Egypt at that time. The historical circumstances requiring a supernatural rescue of the nation from the land of the Nile are missing. Instead, a parallel passage signals that the “Egypt” of Moses and the parting of the Sea is a coded reference to a different land of captivity:

And with thee will I break in pieces the horse and his rider; and with thee will I break in pieces the chariot and his rider ... The sea is come up upon Babylon: she is covered with the multitude of the waves thereof ... My people, go ye out of the midst of her. ... Thus shall Babylon sink, and shall not rise from the evil that I will bring upon her.

Jer 51:21, 42, 45, 64, KJV

⁶⁷ The Heb. first month name Nisan (Est 3:7) was borrowed from Akk. *nīsānnu* (^{ITI}BAR₂), also recorded as ^{ITI}BAR and ^{ITI}BAR.SAG.SAG. The sign BAR (𒍪) is nearly identical to MAŠ (𒍪), but adds the meanings *foreign, to split, to release and set free captives* (Akk. *ašāru*). Sum. **sag.sag** means *slaves*.

⁶⁸ Lexical phrases such as this are treated by modern cuneiform scholars as bilingual dictionary entries. However, the series title invokes Ea as the god who hears the *wailing* (*nâqu*) of supplicants and *sets in motion* (*nâqu*) reversals of fortune. He is also the *pourer of water* (A *naqû*) for the dead, reprising his astral manifestation as GU.LA (forerunner of Aquarius—see Rogers, 1998, pp. 17, 19, 25).

⁶⁹ This proposal suggests a ritual purpose for the otherwise unexplained recurrence of warring twins in the ancestral narratives. In the story of Cain and Abel, the substitute son Seth (Heb. *šēt* → Akk. *šētu*—*this same, to leave someone alive*) restored the lineage after the firstborn Cain was cursed (Gen 4:8-12, 25).

Although the argument for resetting the geographic location of the Exodus to Babylon may initially strike readers as an unwarranted obfuscation of the plain text, there are compelling literary, linguistic and historical reasons for it. Rather than abandoning a venerable tradition, the reversal of this allegorical transposition leads us back to a yet more ancient civilization. Mesopotamia was the crucible in which Judean identity was melted down and from which it was later reforged. Instead of being an unnecessary denial of Egypt (de-nilefication, as it were), the opposite is true. At his symbolic core, Pharaoh is a Euphratean king. This is evident from the Mesopotamian myths that set Moses in motion.

In the Hebraic reworking of the Sumerian and Akkadian legends of Sargon, the infant hero became Moses, while Ur-Zababa became the unnamed Pharaoh. The Egyptian monarch's death by drowning reprised the fate of his Mesopotamian literary forebear. In both the Sargonic template and the Mosaic adaptation, the tyrant's fate is predetermined within a divinely orchestrated plot. The idea that Egypt is allegorical Babylon is signaled *a priori* by the substitution of Pharaoh for Ur-Zababa.

The Unnamed Pharaoh

A striking aspect of “Pharaoh” (פַּרְעֹה) in the Hebrew narratives of Genesis and Exodus is that the king is never named. In the framework of a written composition featuring names that disclose the significance of the character, the absence of a personal name for either Pharaoh or his daughter must be understood as a deliberate narrative device. The nameless Pharaoh appears in multiple generations of the ancestral saga.

In stark contrast, narrative “remembers” the names of the two Hebrew midwives (another ritual pairing) who saved the male newborns (Exod 1:15). The first is Shiphra (*šiprâh*), which corresponds in context to Akkadian *šipru*—signifying *a mission, a messenger, skilled work, a plan, scheme* and the *characteristic activity* of a woman. The second is Puah (*pûâh*), which may be understood as Akkadian *puḫḫu/pa-aḫ-ḫu* (*to give in exchange, to alter the wording of a tablet*).

Puah's role recalls the Mesopotamian ritual of the substitute king (*šar pūḫi*) in which a stand-in was crowned and later killed in place of the true king following the ominous appearance of a lunar eclipse. If the king himself died under the menace of the eclipse, the substitute kept the

throne.⁷⁰ In the Book of Exodus, the death of the firstborn of Egypt took place under the darkened full moon at “half-night” on the half month—the 15th of Nisan (Exod 10:21, 11:4-5, 12:6, 29).⁶⁷ The midwives names and their paired roles in the narrative identify them as magical practitioners who reversed Pharaoh’s curse by substituting his death (and the deaths of the firstborn of all Egypt) for the death decreed for the Hebrew boys.

Like Moses’ two *entu* mothers, the first midwife set the hidden magic in motion, while the second completed it. However, their substitution spell was literally written by the authoring scribe. The narrative decision to name these women by the roles they play within the setting of an allegory suggests proxy magic—the manipulation of figurines imbued with the identities of real world people or entities. In this case, the scribe’s substitution spell would have been directed against its allegorical referent—the King of Babylon.

The episodes of Genesis and Exodus link together to form a narrative arc in which the ancestral protagonists initially live in paradise, then are banished before being divinely led from a land of exile to the future homeland of their descendants. Each character is figurative. Jacob (who is renamed Israel) is literally united Israel. His son Judah is the kingdom of Judah. His son Joseph is the northern kingdom sold (by Judah) into slavery in a foreign land. This saga is narrated from the perspective of the descendants, looking back at the past. The profound ancestral desire to return home therefore belongs to them—the exiled descendants. In this context, the serial appearances of the nameless Pharaoh inform us that he is a symbol—an iterative representation of the same figure.

If we bring this line of reasoning to its logical conclusion, the tyrant was an implacable foe faced by the authors in their own time. Although his identity is veiled, the contemporary villain allegorized as Pharaoh leaves distinctive tracks in the narrative. Moses received his name and his call to office in the symbolic location of AG^{ki}—the *Place of Nabû* and the *Place of the Crown*. Three Neo-Babylonian kings bore the theophoric element Nabû: Nabopolassar (r. 626-605 BC), Nebuchadnezzar II (r. 605-562 BC) and Nabonidus (^dAG.I/^dAK.I) of Harran (r. 556-539 BC). The prominence of Harran and Ur in the ancestral narratives of Genesis tips the evidentiary bucket toward the last king. These two cities were the leading centers of worship of the moon god Sîn, to whom Nabonidus was fanatically devoted.⁷¹

⁷⁰ See Bottéro, 1992, pp. 138-155.

⁷¹ Lewy, 1945.

If Pharaoh is understood as an allegorical stand-in for a Babylonian tyrant, then we must consider Nabonidus (Akk. *Nabû-na'id*) the prime suspect for the unnamed villain of the Exodus—the long sought “Pharaoh of Moses”. The fear of this tyrannical king during the putative mid-6th century era of composition provides a compelling reason for the allegorical substitution of faraway Pharaoh. He is the only historically documented king who both stood in the way of the deported nation’s deep desire to return to its ancestral land and was soundly defeated to make the return possible.

In this light, the inspiration for the Judean scribal decision to replace Nabonidus with “Pharaoh” may be found in his historical contemporary, Aḥmose II (r. 570–526 BC). His name honors the Egyptian moon god *Aaḥ*—making him a very suitable substitute for the moon-besotted tyrant of Babylon. As noted above, Mesopotamian magic commonly involved the manipulation of figurines used as proxies for flesh-and-blood persons. Such rituals were conducted with physical objects, written signs or live people.⁷² The strength of the spell was proportional to the paronomastic power of these associations.⁷³

In this case, the Mesopotamian god *Sîn* was commonly cited by his logogram ^dŠEŠ^{ki}—which can be read as ^dAḤ₂^{ki}. The cuneiform sign AḤ₂/ŠEŠ/URU₃ represents *brother, colleague* (Akk. *aḥu*) in addition to *light* (i.e. the *moon*). The homophone *aḥû* signifies an *outsider* or an *abnormal* form of a known entity.⁷⁴ Another sense of *aḥu* (ZAG) refers to a *half-share* or a joint proprietorship. ZAG is lexical *mišrum* (A I/6:90), which doubly pairs Ur (ŠEŠ^{ki}) and its god (^dŠEŠ^{ki}) with Egypt and *Aaḥ* via the transitive property.⁷⁵ This symbolic correspondence forms a multi-stranded proxy link between the Babylonian monarch and his Egyptian homolog, enhancing the efficacy of the Judean curse.

⁷² Farber (1986) describes “associative magic” in the *bīt rimki* purification ritual in which specific objects were linked to expiatory effects via wordplays. The king meticulously engaged these objects as prescribed in the ritual tablet. The efficacy of his actions derived from the underlying cuneiform double-meanings.

⁷³ An ingenious symbolic linkage in a spell could reveal and invoke a cosmic design that obligated a deity’s cooperation. Farber (ibid. p. 449) cites the *Schenkenliebeszauber* in which a cleverly devised word association gave the spell tablet’s owner an “almost blasphemous” assurance of Ištar’s support.

⁷⁴ In omenology, *aḥû* meant *to become brothers*—in reference to the *pairing off* of two constellations or two anatomical features (of a sacrificed sheep). This was interpreted as *enemies joining forces*.

⁷⁵ ŠEŠ^(ki) = AḤ₂^(ki) → *aḥu* A ≈ *aḥu* B → ZAG → *mišrum*.

It is striking that this suspected substitution of kings is absolute: Nabû-na'id is never mentioned by name in the canonical Hebrew Bible, despite being the monarch whose downfall brought about the historical exodus (from Babylon, not Egypt). The pivotal reign of the last Babylonian king merits a prominent place in Israel's story—which he perhaps has, but only in allegorical disguise. The Hebrew narrative treats Nabonidus as *he-who-must-not-be-named*—the Dark Lord who could only be discussed pseudonymously, lest he leap out of the shadows and seize the fearful speaker.

This dread had a powerful cultural context. Babylonians harbored a great fear of demons, evil omens and capricious changes in the intentions of the gods. They believed that each of these could be dealt with by magical means. The extensive cuneiform record of rituals, incantations and exorcisms designed to ward off such evil attests to this preoccupation. There is also a substantial body of Jewish incantations written in Babylonian Aramaic during the centuries after the return of the exiles.⁷⁶ It follows, then, that practitioners of adversarial magic in Babylon had to take great precautions lest they be discovered—especially in the case of spells directed against the throne. In addition to ordinary spies, the king employed specialists to defend the throne from magical attack—and to control the supernatural landscape.⁷⁷

If we recall the king's chariot guided by the *šēhu* in the Akītu parade, more pieces of the Mosaic puzzle fall into place. The Akītu festival required the physical presence of the king. The Verse Account of Nabonidus tells us that the 12-day national festival of Babylon went unobserved for an entire decade due to his absence (c. 553-543 BC).⁷⁸ The mad monarch earned the deep resentment of the Babylonian populace by leaving the country in a quixotic quest to find the chthonic source of the moon god in Arabia.⁷¹ This concomitantly informs us that Nabonidus rode in the Akītu parade with the *šēhu* in the years before and after his return. It historically attests to the act of ^dAK.I (Nabû-na'id) drawing this particular man forth from the mythic depths of Babylon and making him *šēhu* of the Akītu.

The festival scene offers a compelling cosmological reason for understanding Nabonidus as the pharaonic dueling foe of “Moses”. Under this king, the moon god Sîn was temporarily

⁷⁶ See Naveh, 1998. The Dead Scrolls include several books of magic.

⁷⁷ According to Jean Bottéro, a group of diviners, astrologers, exorcists and priests made up a *de facto* “defense council of the king” (1992, p. 147).

⁷⁸ Beaulieu, 1989, p. 150-151, 206-208.

restored to his ancient place at the head of the pantheon.⁷⁹ This deity was commonly known by the epithet *Lord Zu* (EN.ZU), making him the paronomastic homolog of the fate-seizing monster ^dZû in the Akītu parade. In the eyes of the Judean scholar-scribes watching this grand Babylonian spectacle, the *šēhu* held the tongues of Lord Zu, while Nabonidus rode along oblivious to the mage’s symbolic mastery of his own master.⁸⁰

The Unnamed Šēhu

Moses’ lack of a Hebrew name is matched by his lack of a true personal name. He is given a title that functions as his *nom de guerre*. The mystery surrounding this pseudonym draws our attention to the identity and the ethnicity of the man of who acted as *šēhu* during the reign of Nabonidus. Was he a Judean exile? How did he become *šēhu*? In the biblical account, it was the king’s daughter who gave the Hebrew leader his title. If the Babylonian *šēhu* served as the model for Moses, what was his connection to the *entu* princess-priestess?

Intriguingly, an Aramaic scroll known as the Prayer of Nabonidus (4QPrNab) describes this king’s interactions with an unnamed Judean diviner (Aram. *gʒr*—a reader of extispicy omens).⁸¹ It was discovered in the Qumran caves by the Dead Sea. Although this work did not make it into the canonical scriptures, it overlaps narratively with the account of Daniel, identifying the biblical diviner with the reign of Nabonidus.⁸¹ The story of Daniel describes the rise of a Judean captive to the office of chief sage of Babylon (2:48-49)—a role we might reasonably impute to our *šēhu*. Although the value of the Book of Daniel as a historical document is compromised by multiple mix-ups in the sequence of Babylonian and Persian kings, it (together with 4QPrNab) contributes another piece to our identity puzzle.

⁷⁹ Lewy, 1945 p. 461 calls this the “*Era of the Moon-god*”, which he derives from a Neo-Assyrian phrase translated as “*the distant days of the age of Nannaru*”.

⁸⁰ This interchange may also underlie the allegorical sea serpent Leviathan (*lwytn*), who had to be slain in order for the exiles to return (Isa 27:1, 13). Job identifies *lwytn* as a king (41:1, 34). Akk. *le'ûtum* (A₂.GAL₂ or ZU) refers to royal or divine power. A₂.GAL₂ (MUŠ₂.GAL₂) suggests both *great water* (A.GAL) and *great serpent* (MUŠ.GAL). ZU recalls Sîn as EN.ZU. Heb. *lwytn* may represent Nabonidus envisioned as Alammuš, the underworld (and astral) serpent vizier of Sîn (cf. Job 41: 32-34).

⁸¹ See Steinmann, 2022.

Daniel's account is set in Babylon, yet it reprises many elements of the story of Joseph in Egypt. Joseph was abducted to Egypt and sold as a slave. Daniel was taken as a war captive to Babylon. Both were imbued with the “*spirit of god/the holy gods*” (Gen 41:38/Dan 4:8), recalling the A₂.KAM ideogram of the *šēḫānu*. Both were publically honored by dressing them in fine robes and placing a gold chain around their necks. Intriguingly, Joseph's great skill as a seer and mitigator of fate was rewarded by a parade through cheering Egyptian crowds while riding in (unnamed) Pharaoh's chariot (Gen 41:38-43).

Joseph interpreted an ominous dream of Pharaoh, while Daniel interpreted an ominous dream of Nebuchadnezzar. The latter foretold that the king would go mad and be banished to the wilderness before being restored to the throne (Dan 4:4-36). Although this event is historically unattested for Nebuchadnezzar, it corresponds to Nabonidus' well-documented sojourn in Arabia and decisive return to Babylon.⁸¹ Moses (whose fate was substituted as an infant for Pharaoh's fate) was banished to the wilderness, from which he emphatically returned as the terrifying master magician of Egypt. These themes interlink Moses, Daniel, Joseph and the Judean diviner of 4QPrNab, connecting them to a deliberately hidden dignitary in 6th century Babylon.

The Unnamed Daughter of Pharaoh

Pharaoh's daughter plays a brief but critical role in the Hebraic retelling of the birth of Sargon the Great. A chronicler of Judah later added that Pharaoh's daughter joined the emancipated tribe in its journey back to the ancestral homeland (1 Chr 4:18). This postscript ties the Egyptianized *entu* of the Exodus to a historical personage who deeply sympathized with the Judean exiles and left with them—not from ancient Egypt, but from contemporary Babylon. Although her royal name is withheld, her identity may be deduced from distinctive allegorical details.

If Pharaoh's daughter represents a princess who lived at a time when Judean scribes studied the Birth Legend of Sargon, the only viable candidate is Ennigaldi, daughter of Nabonidus. The king installed her as *entu* of Ur (c. 553 BC) after rebuilding the ancient ziggurat of the moon god that had lain in ruins for centuries. He also magnificently rebuilt the temple of Sîn in his hometown Harran. The twin religious poles of Nabonidus' rule resonate geographically with the biblical iterations of the beautiful woman of Ur/Harran. Like Pharaoh's daughter, each of these

Mesopotamian ladies rejected her father's house and joined the shepherd clan. Each then journeyed to the future land of Judah.⁸²

The matriarch Sarah (Heb. *princess*) was from Ur, the seat of the *entu* priestesshood. Likewise, her successor Rebecca was from Harran, the other Mesopotamian hub of the moon cult. She was the daughter of Bethuel (*bat betû ʿēl*), which may be understood literally as *daughter of the temple* (Heb. *bêt-ʿēl*, Akk. *bītu ilu*).⁸³ In the narrative setting of Harran, *betû ʿēl* implicitly refers to the famed E₂.ĤUL₂.ĤUL₂—the temple of Sîn. In the third generation of matriarchs, Jacob's two wives were daughters of Laban (Heb. *white*). *Labān* is attested in Old Assyrian and Amorite personal names as a lunar theophoric element.⁸⁴

When Jacob saw Rachel (the lovely daughter of Laban) for the first time, he rolled away the enormous round stone blocking the well of Harran, then watered her father's flock and kissed her (Gen 29:10-11). In this carefully staged cultic setting, the round stone metaphorically represents the moon that Jacob (symbolic Israel) had to roll from the *koleós* before he could “kiss” the *entu* and take her away from her lunar father-husband, Laban.⁸⁵

When they escaped from Harran, Laban pursued and entered their tents, ostensibly searching for cultic figurines taken from his house/temple (Gen 31:3-35). When he entered Rachel's tent, she feigned menstruation (a lunar cycle) to physically frustrate her father's attempted repossession. Both daughters chose Jacob (Israel) over their father's house/temple.⁸⁶ After Laban left, Jacob buried the stolen statues, symbolically breaking the enslaving hold of the lunar cult of Ur/Harran upon his family (the 12 tribes of Israel).

⁸² Although no historical evidence for Ennigaldi's participation in her father's overthrow has come to light, the uncontested entry of rebel forces (led by a governor who turned against the king) into Babylon in 539 BC and the abrupt collapse of the Neo-Babylonian Empire signal an “inside job” involving multiple highly placed Babylonians.

⁸³ ^dE₂.DINGIR (*bītu ilu*) is attested in a name from Nippur (Hillprecht and Clay, 1898, BE 9, pl. 75).

⁸⁴ Julius Lewy cites Labanâ-ilâ as an example (1944, p. 434).

⁸⁵ Heb. *nāšaq* (*kiss*) → Akk. *našāqu* (*to kiss, be bodily entwined*) and *nasāqu* (*to choose a share, person, place*). The form *yšq* (Akk. *iššiq*) interchanges with Jacob libating (*yšq*/Akk. *išqi*) life-giving water.

⁸⁶ The narrative uses the Heb. word *ḥēleq* (*portion, division*) with regard to the daughters' choice of Jacob—who is called *ḥālāq* (Gen 27:11). Akk. *ḥalāqu* (ZAḤ) signifies an *escaped slave* or *one who has become a fugitive*. The sign ZAḤ is also BEL (→ *bēl*—*lord, master*).

The fact that the Genesis narrative repeats the acquisition of the Woman of Ur/Harran in three consecutive generations underscores her importance. In each case, a primogenitor of the shepherd clan stole the *entu* from the cult of the moon god—and concomitantly appropriated the fertility, prosperity and glory of Harran (see Gen 30:43-31:16, cf. 12:17-13:2, 26:11-14). The pattern of the foreign priestess joining Israel is repeated in the accounts of Tamar (shrine-prostitute of Timnath), Asenath (daughter of the Egyptian priest of On), Rahab (shrine-prostitute of Jericho, city of the moon) and Ruth of *Moab* (meaning *from father*, referring to Lot of Harran).⁸⁷ Each woman bore a son of destiny.

According to the Birth Legend of Sargon, Mesopotamia's model king was born from an *entu* mother, marking him out for greatness. King David was born from many generations of *entu* mothers, marking him out for extraordinary greatness. Curiously, rather than claiming royal ancestry for their king, the Judean scribes emphasize that both David and his ancestors were shepherds. From Abel (through his replacement Seth) to Shem, Abraham, Isaac, Jacob and Judah, the forebears of Israel's model king herded sheep. Why? The answer lies in the heavenly model for the *entu*.

This divine source is identified in the story of Queen Esther of Persia. Though Jewish, Esther was a foreign queen and another dazzlingly brilliant *entu* heroine of the Bible. She is literally given the name Ištar (*eš₄-tar₂*)⁸⁸—who is Venus, daughter of the Moon. The scroll makes no mention of Yahweh. According to Adin Steinsaltz, this signals “*the hidden hand of Divine Providence*” at work—envisioned as a single male God.⁸⁹ The esteemed rabbi ignores the biblical attestation of the Queen of Heaven as the revered protectress of Judah (see Jer 44:17-18).⁹⁰ In the polytheistic Persian era, the Judean audience would certainly have recognized the numinous nature of Queen Esther as the royal avatar of Ištar/Astarte.

⁸⁷ The respective accounts of these *entu* matriarchs may be found in Gen 38:13-30, 41:45-52, Jos 2:1 (see also the royal tradition recorded Mat 1:5, cf. 1 Chr 2:51) and Rth 4:10-17 (see Gen 11:27, 19:36-37 for her Mesopotamian roots).

⁸⁸ The variant **es₄** is the Sum. sign for *curse* (**aš₂**), which is paired with the verb *to disperse* (**tar**). The symbolism of **es₄-tar₂** underlies Esther's human role in confounding the royal edict to slaughter the Jews.

⁸⁹ Steinsaltz, 2019 (Esther), uses the pronoun **היה** (*him*) and the acronym **יה** (*ha-shem*) for YHWH.

⁹⁰ Despite the adversarial (and anachronistic) editorializing, the Hebrew text acknowledges the goddess' cultural importance and great popularity throughout the monarchal era.

The recurring *entu*-shepherd motif bespeaks a Judean scribal attraction to the Mesopotamian mythology that gave their guardian goddess a critically important backstory. Ištar was the wife of the shepherd god, Tammuz—whom she chose as her mate. The birth order of the figurative founders of the tribes of Israel identifies Judah as the fourth of Jacob’s 12 sons. Jewish commentators have long linked this biblical schema to the 12 months of the year.⁹¹ According to the Babylonian calendar adopted during the exile, the fourth month is Tammuz (Sum. **dumu-zi**, *true son*, also *uprooted son*). This identifies Judah with the shepherd god, making him (and his kingdom) the chosen one of Ištar.⁹²

In Mesopotamian scribal tradition, the “discovery” of symbolic associations was understood as a divine revelation of a cosmic truth.⁹³ The Judean scribes in Babylon recalled that Judah’s original capital of Hebron (where David reigned before becoming king of all Israel) had the pre-Judaic name of Kiryath Arba, which is the *City of Four* (see Jos 14:15, 2 Sam 2:11). This symbolism is foreshadowed by Abraham’s purchase of the ancestral burial cave in Hebron (Gen 23:14-15).⁹⁴ The patriarch was buried precisely in the place where the kingdom of Judah began. It was the grave from which Tammuz would one day rise.

The birthplace of David was Bethlehem, a dozen miles from Kiryath Arba. The Hebrew name *Bêt Leḥem* means *House of Bread*. However, the cuneiform sign for *bread* (NINDA) is also the number *four* (LIMMU). This duality transforms the birthplace of the Davidic dynasty

⁹¹ This idea is attested in the influential *Sefer Yetzirah*, parts of which date to the Talmudic period.

⁹² The eponymous father of the tribe of Judah was chosen by the *q̄dēšāh* Tamar (*date fruit* or *date-palm*) to found the royal line through her (Gen 38:13-29). According to Thorkild Jacobsen (1957), the name Inanna (Sum. predecessor of Ištar) originally meant *Lady of the Date-Clusters*. Even so, Akk. *gišimmaru* (*date-palm*) may be read as ^{giš}*immeru*—the *tree of the ram*. Laffitte (2009) notes that the constellation Aries (Sum. LU₂.ḪUN.GA₂/Dumuzi) was recorded as LU (the *Ram*) prior to the Greek borrowing and recasting of the Mesopotamian Zodiac.

⁹³ See McHugh, 2017, pp. 18-20.

⁹⁴ The price was *four hundred shekels of silver*. The Heb. words *hundred* (constr. state *m^ot*) and *dead* (*mt*) are near homographs. The same double meaning is present in Akkadian, which adds a powerful play upon *silver* (*kaspu*) as a *funerary offering* (*kispu*) while subtly signaling the *casting* (*kašāpu*) of a sorcerer’s *spell* (*kišpu*). Silver (as KI.SAG, phps. Sum. *underworld gift*) signifies the *place of the leader*, but may also mean *place of the slave*. The ideogram for *shekel* (*šiq̄lu*) is also the sign for the royal *crown* (AGA₃/GIN₂)—the grave offering of Abraham at the site of his descendant David’s future crowning.

into the ancient dwelling place of Ištar's husband (*Bêt Lehem = House of Bread* → E₂.NINDA = E₂.LIMMU → *House of Four* → *House/Temple of Tammuz*).⁹⁵ In the worldview of the Judean scribes, this discovery constituted a cosmic truth that obligated Ištar to choose Judah over Babylon and over other nations seeking her cosmic favor.

The *entu* Enheduanna (daughter of Sargon the Great) wrote a hymn to Inanna (the Sumerian cognate of Ištar) that gives us insight into the particular powers they sought:

To interchange the brute and the strong and the weak and the powerless is yours, Inanna.
 To interchange the heights and valleys and the ... and the plains (?) is yours, Inanna. To
 give the crown, the throne and the royal scepter is yours, Inanna. (ETCSL c.4.07.3: 140-
 142)

All of the above suggests that the Judean scribes in Babylon carefully chose Judah's birth order to set in motion a powerful magic for restoring the throne through ancestral identification with Tammuz, the beloved of Ištar.

The sign LIMMU/NINDA moreover represents Akkadian *šakānu*—meaning *to place something for a particular purpose, with particular intention, to arrange a ritual, to place an amulet around the neck, to deposit a tablet for safekeeping*. It corresponds to the funerary offering of Abraham in which the royal crown was symbolically planted in the burial ground of Hebron.⁹⁴ The homophone *sakānu* means *to see to, care for* and *to settle a people*—and to successfully keep them settled.

The biblical account of the interment of father Abraham in the birthplace of the kingdom of Judah in anticipation of the rise of the Davidic dynasty is clearly retrospective. The symbolic connection to the number *four* (of 12) infuses the power of the shepherd Tammuz, who rose from the dead in Mesopotamian myth.⁹⁶ If we recall the paronomastic *tb/tb* sequence of

⁹⁵ Sum. **ninda** is also a rod for measuring out 12 cubits (**kuš₃**). The logogram ^{LÚ}KUŠ signifies a nomadic shepherd. By extension, the measuring rod (Akk. ^{gi}*nindanakku*) may be interpreted as symbol for *reversing the fortunes (nāqu)* of the 12 nomads (NINDA).

⁹⁶ If Tammuz was indeed written into Judah's ancestral history, it signals syncretism with Yahweh—a merging of the Mesopotamian shepherd god with the patron god of the Hebrew shepherd tribe. In western Mesopotamia, Dumuzi was called *šumu* (MU/son) or *šu-um* (MEE IV). The sign MU is also IA₅.

Sargon/Moses, the cuneiform number 12 (TAB.U) signifies *tabû*—*to get up, arise, set out*. The narrative point of reference is the Babylonian exile. The Judean scribes called for the restoration of the nation by highlighting the *entu* matriarchy and shepherd patriarchy of Judah, invoking the ancient cosmic bond between the Queen of Heaven and the Shepherd.⁹⁷

The great goddess was embodied in the *entu* princess-priestess.⁹⁸ Her many biblical roles bear the imprint of the *entu rabû* of 6th century Babylon. In particular, the decision of each of the beautiful women of Ur/Harran to leave her ancestral home and accompany the shepherd in his journey back to his land stands out. It mirrors the reportedly historical choice made by the “*daughter of Pharaoh*” to join the shepherd tribe’s escape from slavery in “*Egypt*” and return to the tribal homeland. It was a journey back to the future. The captivating and enigmatic Ennigaldi of Ur/Harran appears to have been the muse who inspired the Judean scribes in Babylon to write the beautiful *entu* into their biblical allegories.^{82,99}

Conclusion

The biblical account of Moses describes the ancestral wandering of the tribes in the wilderness and their arrival in Canaan. This corresponds to the nation’s historically documented origin as a loose confederation of nomadic tribes that assimilated the sedentary population of the southern Levant during the socio-political reorganization that followed the Late Bronze Age collapse.¹⁰⁰ Moses himself, however, first appears in the Judean rewriting of the Birth Legend of Sargon in the mid-1st millennium.

⁹⁷ The myth (ETCSL c.4.08.33) of Inanna choosing the shepherd Dumuzi over the farmer is retold in the account (Gen 4:3-5) of *Yhwh* favoring the shepherd Abel over the farmer Cain (Kramer, 1961, p. 101-102). Note that Yahu is the anagram of 15 (U.IA₂)—which is the deity number of Inanna/Ištar.

⁹⁸ Although the *entu* of Ur is attested as the ritual embodiment of Ningal (wife of Sîn), Inanna was the daughter of Sîn in the moon cult of Harran. Given the daughter-wife role of the *entu*, Inanna is the divine archetype. She is called ^dnin-e₂-gal-la in a Sum. hymn (ETCSL c.4.07.4), indicating that the ritual roles (and the mythological histories) of the two goddesses overlapped.

⁹⁹ Perhaps we will one day find out that she was not merely a muse, but rather took a key active role in the downfall of her moon-besotted incestuous father and her Machiavellian brother, Belshazzar.

¹⁰⁰ See Finkelstein, 1995, Languet et al., 2013 and Avner, 2021.

This imposes a *terminus a quo* that fundamentally conflicts with the literal reading of the story. Despite the narrative setting in Egypt, the Akkadian vocabulary, cuneiform wordplay and Sargonic themes are fundamentally Mesopotamian. These elements place the author(s) in the 6th century exile of Judah in Babylon—a place and a time where the nation was held and enserfed in a foreign land. This altered chronology begs the question of the Judean authors’ purpose for writing ancestral stories set in the mythological past.

The answer lies in the function of myth in Mesopotamia. Most of the inhabitants of Mesopotamia were illiterate. The common people learned the foundational stories during oral recitations and role-playing performances.¹⁰¹ We see this in the rituals of the Akītu festival, which featured the public reading and reenactment of the Enuma Elish and its interconnected family of myths. The prosperity of Babylon was ritually anchored in the *written* account of Marduk gaining control of the Tablet of Destinies.

In the Babylonian scribal tradition, the present and the future could be altered by manipulating the signs in the ancient tablets that served as cosmic templates. The author of the Enuma Elish used scribal magic to enact a national transformation by authentically transferring the identity of the god who slew the primordial sea serpent from Enlil to Marduk, the patron god of Babylon. The slayer of the serpent gained control of the Tablet of Destinies, thereby obtaining mastery over fate and ensuring the success of his people.

This public practice of written myth in Babylon gives us a window into the worldview of the watching Judean scribes—an exceptionally gifted cohort of exiles who mastered cuneiform in the 6th century (Dan 1:3-4).²⁸ The Judeans noted Babylon’s astonishing resurrection from ashes and subsequent rise to greatest city in the world. The success of this scribal magic provided a model for seeking the restoration of Zion by means of slaying the sea serpent (Isa 51:9-11). Like the author of the Enuma Elish, the Judean scribes in Babylon sought to change their nation’s fate by editing the genetic code of the cosmos (embedded in myth).

If we take a step back and view the full cultural panorama, we see the Judean author of the core Exodus account incorporating the public performance of the Mesopotamian destiny myths into his retelling of the written stories. The scribe transformed the man playing the role of the *šēḫu* in the Akītu parade into the Hebrew sage who mastered the beast of destiny. The *šēḫu* held

¹⁰¹ Lambert and Millard, 1969 p. 8, state “*Oral performance was necessary since the cumbersome system of cuneiform writing restricted literacy to a small elite of professional scribes.*”

the tongues of Zu in his hands under the nose of the unwitting Babylonian king. The scribe thus retained the ritually validated characters of the reenacted myths while substituting their proxy referents.

A 6th century Judean scribe would have found this procedure conveniently laid out in the Birth Legend of Sargon. The story's Neo-Assyrian author ritually replaced the drowning of the illegitimate Sargon (representing Sargon II) with the drowning of Ur-Zababa (representing Shalmanezar V). The Judean scribe substituted the drowning of Pharaoh (Nabonidus) in exchange for the drowning of Moses (the *šēhu*). Due to the risk of public exposure, the adversarial magic directed against the Babylonian king was concealed by disguising the tyrant as Pharaoh and the setting as Egypt.¹⁰²

To actualize this ritual substitution (in heaven and on earth), the Judeans enlisted powerful Mesopotamian deities to supplement Yahweh. Each had to be capable of reversing the nation's fate and each had to be subject to Judah's claim upon their patronage. They called upon Ea, the master of all knowledge (ZU), to defeat EN.ZU—the pretentious moon god who held the nation captive in Nabonidean Babylon.^{51,52,68,103} They called upon Ištar, daughter of Sîn and *entu* of the gods, to work wonders through the *entu* daughter of the king.^{90,97,98} Finally, they called upon Tammuz—the shepherd who rose from the underworld—to bring Judah back from the dead.^{92,95,96} The scribes invoked and obligated each of these “Yah” deities by establishing their ancient ties to the nation.

Postscript

The fact that many myths were incorporated into the ancestral narrative was obviously known by the scribes who composed the accounts, along with their peers. Deutero-Isaiah reveals that

¹⁰² The similarities in the mythic form and function of Genesis, Exodus, Ruth and Job suggest a circle of exilic scribes working together to set in motion a reversal of their nation's fate.

¹⁰³ The Judean scribes located a primordial *casus belli* between Ea and Sîn in the account of Ninti (*Lady Rib/Lady Life*) in Dilmun (ETCSL c.1.1.1), whom they transposed to Eve in Eden. She was removed from her rib-father Enki and declared priestess of the moon (^dNin-ti nin iti-e he₂-a), making her the first *entu*. In this backstory of Inanna/Ištar, the great goddess is revealed to be Ea's daughter-wife taken by Sîn.

the story of the splitting of the sea began as an invocation of the Levantine goddess who cleaved the primordial sea serpent, asking that she bring back a remnant to Zion (Isa 51:9-11).⁵⁶ The psalmist Asaph was aware of the interrelationship between the smiting of the serpent, the dividing of the sea and opening a passage through which the nation might return (Psa 74:7-15, 77:15-20). Jeremiah knew that the sea serpent was metaphorical Babylon (Jer 51:34/44). The prophet's allegory was incorporated into a written curse that was ritually enacted by casting it into the Euphrates River (Jer 51:60-64). This anecdote discloses the practice of magic that underlies the Judean recrafting of primordial myth. Nevertheless, by the Roman era the memory of these origins had largely dropped out of Jewish consciousness.

After the exiles returned from Babylon, Moses' original purpose was fulfilled. The geopolitical and ritual context of Genesis-Exodus (known mostly by scribes) was gradually lost. The textual severance likely began with the transfer of the core exilic compositions from clay tablets to scrolls. Concomitantly, the original cuneiform texts (opaquely remembered in the Talmud as *ašurit*—*Assyrian*) were transcribed in the Aramaic script (see Sanhedrin 22a:1-3). Moses was subsequently made (via expansion of the scrolls) the authority for a strict new socio-religious code that would (hopefully) ensure that Judah would never again be deported.¹⁰⁴ This orthopraxy was broadly adopted under the Hasmonean priest-kings.¹⁰⁵ From that point forward, Moses was culturally fixed as the historical figure who transformed the tribes of Israel into a Torah-observant nation.

¹⁰⁴ Moses had the initial teaching role (Exod 31:18) of bringing the nation the *tablets of the ʿēdūt*, corresponding to Akk. *edūtu* (*knowledge*). These were also called *tablets of stone* (Akk. *abnu/IA₄*). This reprises the role of the *apkallu* sages who were serially sent by the creator Ea to teach humanity the arts of civilization (see Reiner, 1961, for the miracles performed by these sages). The *apkallu* emerged from the water (the sentient ZU.AB), which we also see with Moses (and later Jesus).

¹⁰⁵ The Hasmoneans appear to have seized upon this transformation as a political opportunity. By asserting the binding nature of the Mosaic Law, they justified their sacerdotal rule and preempted the restoration of the living heirs of David. The claim (by allied scribes) that the Torah existed from ancient Egypt onward provided grounds for attacking the kings of Israel and Judah for failing to follow its edicts—and for apostatizing the theocratic ideal (see 1 Sam 8:4-9).

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